

MARE/2014/41

SaFENet

**Sustainable Fisheries in EU Mediterranean waters
through network of MPAs**

Deliverable 4.2

Report describing the quantitative models

By M. Coll, D. Vilas, X. Corrales, C.Piroddi, J. Steenbeek

*WORK PACKAGE 4 – SCENARIOS OF FISHERIES MANAGEMENT AND
ECOSYSTEM SUSTAINABILITY USING MPA NETWORKS*

(Resp. M.Coll, EII-CSIC)

*Activity 4A - Quantification of main structural and functional features of
Mediterranean ecosystems associated with a network of protected areas
(Resp. M. Coll, EII-CSIC)*

*Task 4A-2. To quantitatively describe the structure and functioning, with
emphasis on their interactions with fisheries*

Contents

Introduction.....	3
Methodology	3
Methodological strategy.....	3
Description of study areas.....	6
Summary of Ecopath modelling methodology	11
Summary of data collection and integration	12
Summary of modelling analyses and indicators used	13
Modelling Results	16
Local models: MUs and MPAs.....	16
FRA models of the Gulf of Lions and ZTB Artengario.....	30
Sub-regional model of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea.....	39
Regional model of the Western Mediterranean Sea.....	47
Discussion and conclusions	55
Local models: Mus, MPAs and FRAs	55
Sub-regional and regional models.....	55
Quality of the data to develop food-web models	56
Annexes – Supplementary material from the ecological models.....	57
Supplementary material – Cèrbere-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands MU models....	57
Supplementary material – Cèrbere-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands MPA models..	57
Supplementary material – FRAs Ecopath models	57
Supplementary material – Northwestern Mediterranean Sea Ecopath model	57
Supplementary material – Western Mediterranean Sea Ecopath model.....	58
References.....	59

Introduction

Ecological modelling has emerged as a highly suitable tool to integrate available biological data with the final objective to obtain insights how ecosystems are structured, how they function and how they deliver ecosystem services (Christensen & Maclean 2011, Link 2011). This overall ecosystem picture is the first step to move towards the development of future scenarios for sustainable use of marine ecosystem services (Fulton et al. 2015b).

Previous studies to model MPAs have identified the need to assess trophic dynamics and the size of MPAs when quantifying the impact of protection on fisheries (Walters 2000, Fulton et al. 2015a), also in the Mediterranean Sea (Libralato et al. 2010), and the usefulness of ecosystem modelling as simulation tools to understand MPA dynamics (Christensen 2013). However, the investigation of the potential benefits of network of MPAs, which has been highlighted to be essential from a management perspective (Sala et al. 2002), has not yet been fully developed using food web modelling.

In WP4 we used a combination of advanced qualitative (*deliverable 4.1*) and quantitative ecological modelling techniques (*this deliverable and deliverables 4.3 and 4.4*) to assess how Mediterranean ecosystems associated with networks of management units (i.e., MPAs *sensu lato*) are structured, how they function, and how they can sustain present conditions and future change of fisheries exploitation rates and patterns in a sustainable way. In particular, we developed food-web models to describe the networks of MPAs in the study area from where we developed management scenarios to analyze the impact of exploitation of targeted stocks to their sustainable levels. Novel spatial-temporal modelling approaches were implemented to capture the complex dynamics between exploitation and conservation using networks of MPAs. The term ‘MPA’ in this study was broadly applied to consider both formal MPAs and areas surrounding MPAs, and included areas where other sources of reduction of fisheries exploitation occur, such as seasonal-temporal closures, closures of exploitation of specific species, and reductions of fishing effort.

The overall objective of activity 4A was to develop a series of food-web models representing Mediterranean Sea ecosystems associated with networks of MPAs and other management measures to assess the impact of these areas on fisheries production and sustainability. After the qualitative food-web modelling approach was developed (*deliverable 4.1*), results were used to develop quantitative modelling with the aim to (i) quantify the main structural and functional traits of studied ecosystems, and (ii) assess how exploitation and protection regimes impact these ecosystems. In this deliverable we explain the development of the local, sub-regional and regional quantitative Ecopath models (Christensen & Walters 2004, Coll et al. 2015) developed under Safenet, presenting basic analysis of results. These quantitative models were the basis from where to perform simulations of the configuration of the network/(s) of protected areas considering different geographic scales and including spatial connectivity/dispersal patterns between areas and the impact of fisheries restriction areas in the study regions and including the open ocean. This was pursued developing spatial-temporal fisheries simulations using a series of advanced spatial modelling tools (e.g., scenario generator, habitat capacity model, spatial-temporal framework, etc.) which are presented in *deliverable 4.3 and 4.4*.

Methodology

Methodological strategy

To develop quantitative food-web models we used the Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) modelling approach (Christensen & Walters 2004, Coll et al. 2015), version 6.6, building on data and results from WP2 and WP3, in addition to other available information from the literature and previous projects. The food-web models developed under WP4 represent Mediterranean marine food webs

including both commercial and non-commercial species as a foundation to examine ecosystem dynamics. However, a special emphasis was put on commercial species relevant for large scale fisheries, and small scale (artisanal) and recreational fisheries. The models considered coastal and off-shore areas, and the pelagic compartment was also explicitly represented to design and analyze meaningful scenarios of fisheries management and ecosystem sustainability together.

The structure of all the models was based on the meta-web structure developed for the Western Mediterranean Sea, presented in **deliverable 4.1** (Figure 1). This structure was applied to the different models developed in WP4 to standardize the modelling procedure and to ensure consistency between models.

Previously EwE models developed in the Mediterranean Sea were revised (Coll & Libralato 2012, Colléter et al. 2015). Models developed in the coastal areas of the Mediterranean Sea representing MPAs were identified and examined for structure, parametrization strategy and sources of information (e.g., Pinnegar et al. 2000, Mellado López 2006, Albouy et al. 2010, Valls et al. 2012, Prato et al. 2014, Prato 2016). The sub-regional and regional modelling efforts developed under Safenet benefitted from previous large modelling applications in the Mediterranean Sea (e.g., the Northwestern Mediterranean Model and the Mediterranean Model available, Corrales et al. 2015, Piroddi et al. 2015).

Figure 1. Meta-web structure of the Western Mediterranean marine food web (deliverable 4.1 – Safenet project).

developed under Safenet benefitted from previous large modelling applications in the Mediterranean Sea (e.g., the Northwestern Mediterranean Model and the Mediterranean Model available, Corrales et al. 2015, Piroddi et al. 2015).

Three geographic scales were used during the ecosystem modelling development: a local scale (using individual case studies of management units and local MPAs and surrounding areas), a sub-regional scale (aggregating case studies into a network of MPAs and surrounding area), and a regional scale (modelling all the study area together and considering the presence of all the MPAs located within the study area) (Table 1 and Figure 2).

Overall, under WP4 we developed 17 Ecopath food web models: 14 corresponding to local areas (MPAs or FRAs), two corresponding to the sub-regional model area, and the last model representing the whole Western Mediterranean Sea (Table 1). The models included between 63 to 90 functional groups, covered various depth ranges, and included coastal to deep-sea and pelagic ecosystems. Of those models, nine corresponded to management units (MUs) of three MPAs: fully protected areas (FPA), partially protected areas (PPA) or unprotected areas around the MPA (UPA) of three MPAs: Cerbère-Banyuls MPA, Cap de Creus MPA and Medes Islands MPA. We selected the unprotected areas (UPAs) surrounding the MPAs in order to model a similar ecosystem without protection but with immediate influence from the protected region. We defined unprotected areas as those areas adjacent to existing MPAs with similar characteristics to the area within the MPA. For the Cerbère-Banyuls MPA, Cap de Creus MPA and Medes Islands MPAs, the MU models were integrated into three models of the whole MPAs. These three models were also fitted to time series and used to develop spatial-temporal simulations (deliverables 4.3 and 4.4). In addition, models of two Fisheries Restricted Areas (FRAs) in the Western Mediterranean Sea were developed, one representing the

Gulf of Lions FRA (in France) and the other representing the “Zona di Tutela Biologica” Argentario FRA (in Italy). These two models were fitted to time series and used to develop temporal simulations (*deliverable 4.3*).

The three MPA models of Cerbère-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands were aggregated into a larger sub-regional model that included also the non-protected sub-regional area of the surroundings (*Figure 2*). This model was called sub-regional Northwestern Mediterranean Sea model and it was fitted to time series and used to develop spatial-temporal simulations to assess the impact of a potential network of MPAs within the region (*deliverables 4.3 and 4.4*) (*Table 1*). Finally, all the information used to develop the local and sub-regional models was complemented and used to develop the Western Mediterranean Sea model, which represented the whole Western basin and was fitted to time series and used to develop spatial-temporal models (*deliverables 4.3 and 4.4*) (*Table 1*).

Table 1. Models developed with Ecopath (*deliverable 4.2*), Ecosim (*deliverable 4.3*), and Ecospace (*deliverable 4.4*) in WP4. The key features of the models are highlighted. FPA: Fully protected areas; PPA: Partially protected areas; UPA: Unprotected areas around the MPA; FRA: Fisheries Restricted Areas; MUs: Management units within the MPAs (FPA, PPA or UA).

Food web model	Functional groups	Area	km ²	Base year	Depth range (m)	Ecopath	Ecosim*	Ecospace	Scenarios
Local models - FRAs, MUs & MPAs									
FPA Cerbère-Banyuls MPA	63	FPA	0.65	2013	0-50	X			
PPA Cerbère-Banyuls MPA	63+1	PPA	5.85	2013	0-50	X			
UPA Cerbère-Banyuls MPA	63+1	UPA	35	2013	0-50	X			
Whole Cerbère-Banyuls MPA	63+1	whole	41.5	2013	0-50	X	X	X	X
FPA Cap de Creus MPA	66	FPA	0.21	2005-08	0-50	X			
PPA Cap de Creus MPA	66+1	PPA	7.98	2005-08	0-50	X			
UPA Cap de Creus MPA	66+1	UPA	22.37	2005-08	0-50	X			
Whole Cap de Creus MPA	66+1	whole	30.56	2005-08	0-50	X	X	X	X
FPA Medes MPA	66	FPA	0.393	2000-04	0-50	X			
PPA Medes MPA	66+1	PPA	4.243	2000-04	0-50	X			
UPA Medes MPA	66+1	UPA	14.85	2000-04	0-50	X			
Whole Medes MPA	66+1	whole	19.486	2000-04	0-50	X	X	X	X
FRA Gulf of Lions (CoSeGoL)	72	whole	2051	2006-08	100-1500	X	X		X
FRA ZTB Argentario	68	whole	50	2002-04	150-220	X	X		X
Subregional model - NW network									
Non protected subregional	69	UPA	540	2008-10	0-100	X			
Subregional	69	whole	614	2008-10	0-100	X	X	X	X
Regional model - Western Mediterranean Sea									
Western Mediterranean	90	whole	846002	1990	all	X	X	X	X

**fitted to data.*

Description of study areas

Below we summarize main features of the study areas representing the Ecopath food-web models developed in WP4 (Table 1).

Cerbère-Banyuls Marine Protected Area (MPA)

The Cerbère-Banyuls MPA covers a coastal area of 6.5 km² in the NW Mediterranean Sea, south-eastern part of France (Gabrié et al., 2012) (Figure 3). This marine area comprises a deep range between 0 and 60 metres and it contains three main Mediterranean habitats: calcareous seaweed bottom (*Lithophyllum*), mediterranean seagrass meadows (*Posidonia oceanica*) and coralligenous bottom (*Pseudolithophyllum expansum*). A number of protected and emblematic species of the Mediterranean Sea inhabit this MPA, such as dusky grouper (*Epinephelus marginatus*) and red coral (*Corallium rubrum*). The MPA was established in 1974, and its creation was vital to counteract the coastal damage caused by tourism, fishing and pollution. Its mission was to preserve original local habitats and their biodiversity, to regulate human activities, to promote the “reserve effect”, to help research, to

contribute to the preservation of artisanal fishery, and to inform the public about the importance of the environment and sensibly promote the local economy (Di Franco et al. 2014).

This marine reserve is split in two areas, which are differentiated by the level of protection (Figure 3). The fully protected area (FPA) occupies an area of 0.65 km², where all fishing activities, scuba diving and anchoring are forbidden, except those necessary for scientific research authorized by the Reserve's Consultative Committee. The partial protected area (PPA) has a greater surface area than the FPA (5.85 km²), and some activities are regulated, such as fishing, while others are forbidden, such as underwater spearfishing. In PPA, recreational fishing is allowed between sunrise and sunset and regulated: only holders of a written authorization issued by the Maritime Office «Affaires Maritimes» and the Marine Reserve. On the other hand, artisanal fishing activity is allowed only with authorization and a maximum of 15 boats, mainly composed by Port-Vendres artisanal fleet (Di Franco et al. 2014). Therefore, we set the boundaries of the outside part of the MPA, considering the bathymetry range and the habitat structure, so we defined an unprotected (UPA) area of 35 km².

Regional Natural Park Cap de Creus

Cap de Creus is located in the north-eastern coast of Spain (Figure 4), and its marine protected area has a depth range between 0 and 60 metres. Shallow marine bottoms surrounding the peninsula of Cape de Creus are mostly rocky whereas most deep areas are muddy (Gómez et al. 2006). The coastal rocky bottoms of the Cap de Creus continental shelf are dominated by coralligenous communities, mainly characterized by coralline algae and suspension feeders species (gorgonians, sponges, and bryozoans) (Iacono et al. 2012). This MPA, which was created in 1998, covers a total surface area of 30.56 km², and it is composed by three areas depending on the protection level (Figure 4). The Natural Park of Cap de Creus was created to protect the environment and the traditional activities in this area, and to help rebuild and protect exploited stocks and habitats.

The unprotected area (UPA) occupies 22.37 km², the PPA 7.98 km², whereas the FPA covers 0.21 km².

Trawling and purse-seine is forbidden in the whole natural park, and artisanal and recreational fishery (spearfishing, shore fishing and angling) is permitted except in the FPA. The bulk of the fishing fleet of Cape Creus is composed of artisanal vessels up to 6 metres in length, and come from different villages (Roses, Port de la Selva, Cadaqués and Llançà) (Gómez et al. 2006).

Figure 4. Location of the different management areas of Regional Natural Park Cap de Creus.

Medes Islands Marine Protected Area (MPA)

The Medes islands is composed by seven islands and located one mile off the town of l’Estartit (Spain), in the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea (Figure 5). Medes Islands MPA has a depth range from 0 to 60 metres, and it contains a great biodiversity, constituting a complex ecosystem due to the existence of many different types of seabed and marine environment, such as: *Posidonia oceanica* meadows, gorgonian communities (*Eunicella singularis* and *Paramuricea clavata*), and coralligenous bottom (Ros & Gili 2015). Therefore, it shelters other important marine species, like dusky grouper or red coral (Hereu & Quintana 2012). The main objective for the establishment of this MPA was similar to Cèrbere-Banyuls: to preserve the original habitats and their biodiversity, to regulate human activities, to promote the “reserve effect”, to help research, to contribute to the preservation of artisanal fisheries, and to inform the public about the importance of the environment and sensibly promote the local economy (Hereu & Quintana 2012).

Figure 5. Location of the different management areas of Medes Islands MPA.

This MPA, which was created in 1983, covers a surface area of 4.64km² and is split in two different areas with different protection levels (FPA and PPA) (Figure 5). The FPA (0.393 km²) is situated in the core, surrounding the islands, where all fishing and anchoring activity is forbidden. In the PPA (4.24 km²), only artisanal fishery (longlines and trammel nets) is permitted, but regulated, while recreational fishery is banned in this area too. The main fleet operating in the surrounding area of Medes Islands are from l’Estartit harbour (Martín et al. 2012). Therefore, we defined the boundaries of the outside unprotected area neighbouring the MPA based on similarity in bathymetry range, habitat structure. The UPA includes a section of the Natural Park of Montgrí. The resulting UPA has a surface area of 14.85 km².

The Fisheries Restricted Area (FRA) of the Continental slope of the Eastern Gulf of Lion

The GoL FRA is enclosed in the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea, inside the boundaries of the following geographic coordinates: 42°40'N, 4°20' E; 42°40'N, 5°00' E; 43°00'N, 4°20' E; 43°00'N, 5°00' E (Figure 6). The Gulf of Lion is one of the most productive regions of the Mediterranean Sea because of the considerable inputs from the Rhone river and an annual upwelling process (Raimbault & Durrieu de Madron 2003). The bathymetry of GoL FRA ranges from 100 to 1500 metres and it covers a surface area of 2051 km² (Massutí et al. 2008). Also, this area is characterised by an intricate network of submarine canyons (Canals et al., 2004), and important benthonic communities of echinoderms, gorgonians and sponges (UNEP-MAP-RAC/SPA 2013).

Figure 6. Location of the Fisheries Restricted Area (FRA) Continental slope of the Eastern Gulf of Lion.

This FRA is exploited by Spanish bottom trawlers, Spanish longliners, French midwater trawlers and French gillnets. French trawlers are the main component of the fleet exploiting the marine resources of the Gulf of Lion, which can be divided in two main components: one directed to the catch of small pelagic fishes, and the other exploiting a great diversity of demersal species (UNEP-MAP-RAC/SPA 2013).

In 2009, the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM) adopted the establishment of a FRA in the Gulf of Lion to protect spawning aggregations and

deep sea sensitive habitats (GFCM, 2009). In this recommendation, GFCM called for ensuring that fishing effort for demersal stocks of vessels using towed nets, bottom and mid-water longlines, bottom-set nets shall not exceed the level of fishing effort applied in 2008 in the FRA CoSEGoL. Thus, the aim of this FRA was to protect very important spawning stocks of several species of fishes of paramount importance in the North Western Mediterranean fisheries, affecting mainly France and Spain, as mentioned above. The main effect of protecting spawners is to supply recruits of main target species (*Merluccius merluccius*, *Lophius piscatorius*, *Nephrops norvegicus* and *Aristeus antennatus*), and conserve accompanying species (*Micromesistius poutassou* and *Lepidopus caudatus*) in order to maintaining the trophic web structure (UNEP-MAP-RAC/SPA 2013).

Fisheries Restricted Area (FRA) of “Zona di Tutela Biologica” (ZTB) Argentario

The FRA ZTB Argentario is located in the northern Tyrrhenian Sea, inside the following geographical coordinates: 42°20'N, 10°50'E; 42°23'N, 10°50'E; 42°20'N, 10°44'E; 42°23'N, 10°44'E (Figure 7). It is the smallest FRA in the Mediterranean Sea, covering a surface area of 50 km² and its bathymetry ranges from 150 to 220 metres. Regarding habitat, this area is characterised by its muddy detritic bottom biocoenosis, with important benthonic communities of *Leptometra phalangium*, *Funicula quadrangularis* and the massive presence of the mysid *Lophogaster typicus*, which seems a key element in the diet of juveniles of many fish species (Cinuzzi 2005).

Figure 7. Location of the Fisheries Restricted Area (FRA) “Zona di Tutela Biologica” (ZTB) Argentario.

This area is generally exploited by industrial and recreational fisheries, in particular Italian industrial trawlers. Essentially, this fleet is composed by Porto Santo Stefano (PSS) trawlers, which represents one of the most important fishing fleets along the western Italian coasts, and it accounts for almost the 60% of the vessels exploiting the fishing grounds of the Tyrrhenian Sea (Ligas et al. 2010). Although FRA ZTB Argentario was established by Italian Ministry decree in 1988 (MD – 21th of July, 1988), real enforcement started only in 2005 (Ligas & Sartor, personal comm. 2017). In fact, only few years later, another Ministry decree in 2009 (MD - 22th of January, 2009) re-opened the fishing activity in the FRA. This last decree regulates recreational (maximum of 5 hooks per person) and industrial fishery (otter bottom trawling and pelagic trawling are forbidden in the first part of the year: from 1 January to 30 June. The use of the others gears such as longlines, purse seine, set nets and traps is permitted all year). The main reason to set up this FRA was the protection of juveniles of many commercial demersal fish species, such as: *Merluccius merluccius*, *Mullus barbatus*, *Trisopterus capellanus*, *Illex coindetii*, *Eledone cirrhosa* and *Parapenaeus longirostris* (Cinuzzi, 2005).

Northwestern Mediterranean network model

The NW Mediterranean region selected in WP4 covers a total area of 614 km² (Table 1 and Figure 2). Of those, the majority of the area is non-protected, and a small fraction of it is covered by the MPAs of Cerbère-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands in France and Spain (Figure 8 and 9). This model represents an area that could potentially host a network of MPAs and as such the model was developed to test this hypothesis. The depth range of the model includes an area from the coast to 100 meters of depth and hosts a diversity of fisheries activities, including industrial, artisanal and recreational fisheries, mostly from Spain but also from France.

Figure 8. Location of the local MPAs of Cerbère-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands in the NW Mediterranean Sea and unprotected areas of the model.

Regional model: Western Mediterranean Sea

Finally, the regional model representing the Western Mediterranean Sea covered a total area of 84.6002 km² with depth ranges including coastal to deep sea areas (Figure 9). The model covered both European and non-European waters with the aim to create a comprehensive representation of the Western Mediterranean sub-basin. Data to build the baseline model was mainly collected from the 1990s and included data from WP2, WP3, online databases and from the literature.

Summary of Ecopath modelling methodology

The basic routine of Ecopath with Ecosim is the Ecopath model. It provides a snapshot of the structure and flows of a food web and describes the balance between production of functional groups and all consumptions within an ecosystem (Polovina 1984, Christensen & Pauly 1992). Each functional group can represent a species, a sub-group of a species (e.g. juveniles and adults) or a group of species that have functional and ecological similarities.

The *Ecopath* model uses a system of linear equations to describe the average flows of mass and energy between these groups during a period of time, normally a year. The flow to and from each group is described by the following equation:

$$B_i \cdot (P/B)_i = \sum B_j \cdot (Q/B)_j \cdot DC_{ij} + Y_i + E_i + BA_i + B_i \cdot (P/B)_i \cdot (1 - EE_i) \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where B_i is the biomass of group i , P/B_i is the production per unit of biomass, Y_i is the total fishery catch rate, E_i is the net migration rate (emigration–immigration), BA_i is the biomass accumulation rate, EE_i is the Ecotrophic Efficiency', or the proportion of the production that is utilized in the system, B_j is the biomass of consumers or predators j , $(Q/B)_j$ is the consumption per unit of biomass of j , and DC_{ij} is the fraction of i in the diet of j . To parameterize an *Ecopath* model it is required a series of inputs for each functional group i , mostly Biomass (B_i), Diet (DC_{ij}), consumption and production per unit of biomass (Q/B_i and P/B_i), and fishing yields and other exports (Y_i and E_i).

Among B, P/B, Q/B, EE, the model can estimate one parameter and the others are mandatory inputs (Christensen & Walters 2004, Christensen et al. 2008).

For a model, the energy input and output of all functional groups must be balanced under some ecological and thermodynamic rules: (1) $EE < 1.0$; (2) P/Q [production/consumption rate or gross efficiency (GE)] ranges from 0.1 to 0.3 with the exception of fast growing groups such as bacteria; (3) R/A (respiration/food assimilation) < 1 ; (4) R/B (respiration/biomass) ranges from 1 to 10 for fishes and higher values for small organisms; (5) NE (net efficiency of food conversion) $> GE$ and (6) P/R (production/respiration) < 1 (Heymans et al. 2016). Initial values of the models showed that the $EE < 1$ for some functional groups, mostly pelagic fish groups, invertebrates and cephalopod groups. To balance the models, we applied a manual mass-balanced procedure following top-down approach modifying appropriate input parameters (starting from the functional groups with higher trophic level) and following the best practice guidelines provided in the literature (Heymans et al. 2016). In order to ensure that the models were following the general ecological and fishery principles we used PREBAL diagnostics (Link, 2010). PREBAL is a plugin inside EwE and let identify issues of model structure and data quality before balancing procedure. The PREBAL criteria include some “rules of thumbs” such as the assumption that biomass, P/B and Q/B should decrease from lower to higher trophic levels (Link 2010).

Summary of data collection and integration

We parameterized the 17 food web models (Table 1) using the meta-web structure define in the qualitative modelling exercise (Figure 1). Each local, sub-regional and regional model included all metaweb functional groups present in the area, and initial parameters were obtained from data provided in WP2, WP3 and available in the literature. Ecopath parameter summaries are provided in the supplementary materials of the Annex section for each model. We parameterized the 17 food web models using methodologies similar to earlier studies of marine ecosystems in the Mediterranean Sea (e.g., Pinnegar et al. 2000, Coll 2006, Mellado López 2006, Coll et al. 2007, Albouy et al. 2010, Valls et al. 2012, Prato et al. 2014, Corrales et al. 2015, Piroddi et al. 2015, Prato 2016, Corrales et al. 2017).

The biomasses of the functional groups were obtained from different sources (e.g., MEDIAS pelagic survey, MEDITS benthic trawling survey, underwater visual census conducted during the project or before and reported in WP3, literature information and data from online databases). Data were collected from the study areas or surrounding areas.

Because of lack of local data, and because of their close proximities, the nine MU MPA models shared biomass data for some FGs (marine mammals, seabirds, sea turtles, pelagic fish, some invertebrates' groups, primary producers, zooplankton and phytoplankton). For all other functional groups, the MU models were parameterized with local information obtained from field studies. Biomass estimates for invertebrates' species were not available in several cases and therefore we either used realistic EE values to estimate their biomass, or we extracted biomass data from other models covering the same areas. Some biomass data of pelagic fish groups in the local models was scaled to attain more accurate biomass estimations for coastal areas, where scaling conversions were based on species depth distributions (extracted from Aquamaps – www.aquamaps.org) taking into account species contributions to the overarching functional groups. For those FGs without biomass data in some local area/s of the MPA (FPA, PPA and/or UPA), we calculated biomasses based on assumptions, rules and scaling factors. We used a criterion proposed by Claudet et al. (Claudet & Fraschetti 2010), based on the behaviour (demersal or pelagic), the commercial value (commercial and non-commercial) and the size of species.

MEDITS trawling survey data was analysed and data was extracted with a custom software tool built for Safenet. MEDITS data explorer (Steenbeek 2018b) allowed extraction of MEDITS data easily,

weighting it by the bathymetry strata were the species occurred. For the local models, we extracted MEDITS trawling survey data from the closest point to MPA in order to have biomass data for those species which were not present during underwater visual census fieldwork. Those species are present in the MPAs, but they are less important in MPAs in terms of biomass. This assumption was assessed previously by expert knowledge. For the sub-regional and regional models, the MEDITS trawling survey data was extracted weighted by the strata, so the estimate represented the unequal contribution of each strata to the study area.

Production rate (P/B , year^{-1}) and consumption rate (Q/B , year^{-1}) rates were either estimated using empirical equations (Heymans et al. 2016) or taken from literature or from other models (supplementary material). Additionally, local body lengths of reef-associated species obtained from UVC (Di Franco personal communication) were used to estimate those rates using empirical equations and local data (Pauly 1980). In some cases, these produced different rates between MUs due to changes in the length frequency of species in protected versus not protected areas.

Diet information was compiled using published (supplementary material) on stomach content analyses, giving preference to local or similar areas. Another custom-built extraction tool for Safenet, Diet matrix calculator (Steenbeek 2018a), automatizes the process of selecting and scaling diet data. Drawing on a large library of published diet studies, Diet matrix calculator selects the most likely suitable diet studies for a specific model area, based on a range of criteria, and generates a diet composition matrix with accompanying pedigree index for each predatory functional group. For local models, we set a fraction of the diet composition as import for all MUs based on the time that these species feed outside the system (Heymans et al. 2016). This assumption was based on the size, behaviour and ecology of species of each functional group.

Fisheries data were obtained from different sources (public database from GFCM and FAO, literature and DCF data provided by WP2) and were split into different fishing fleets. For the local models, we separated recreational and artisanal fleets (except for FPA models where fishing activities are not allowed). Regarding artisanal catches, Cerbère-Banyuls catches were obtained from (Prats 2016), while catches for Cap de Creus and Medes were obtained from official datasets of the regional government of Catalonia, managed by the Institute of Marine Sciences (ICM-CSIC) (Tudó 2017). For Cap de Creus, landings data were obtained from Llança, Port de la Selva, Cadaques and Roses - the harbour of the main fishing fleet. Annual landings were scaled to the number of fished months inside the MPA (Gómez et al. 2006). For recreational fishery, we extracted catches from Ivanhoff et al. (Ivanoff et al. 2010) in Cerbère-Banyuls. Cap de Creus catches came from Font and Lloret (Font & Lloret 2011b, Font & Lloret 2011a), and Lloret (Lloret et al. 2008a, Lloret et al. 2008b, Lloret et al. In press). For Medes recreational catches were collected from Sacanell (Sacanell 2012). Fisheries data for the FRA models, the sub-regional models and the regional model were obtained from the official dataset of the EU Commission from the DFC as provided by WP2, and from the in house datasets of the Institute of Marine Science (ICM) of CSIC.

To balance the models, we applied a manual mass-balanced procedure following a top-down approach modifying input parameters starting from the functional groups with higher TL and considering the best practice guidelines (Heymans et al. 2016). Several functional groups displayed low P/Q values (<0.2 or even <0.1 in some cases), and reasonable P/Q values were assigned based on a previous EwE model developed in the same study area (Corrales et al. 2015).

Summary of modelling analyses and indicators used

The quality of the models was estimated by calculating **the pedigree index**, a summary of the quality of input parameters used to parameterize the model for which each input is associated to a confidence interval (Christensen & Walters 2004, Heymans et al. 2016). This information was first used to identify parameters of lower quality and thus could be modified during the balancing procedure. The

resulting pedigree index of the overall model, which vary between 0 (lowest quality) and 1 (highest quality), was used to derive confidence intervals to proceed with uncertainty analyses in Ecosim and Ecospace using Monte Carlo simulations routine (*deliverables 4.3 and 4.4*).

After the Ecopath models were balanced and their quality was assessed, we extracted several indicators. We used the **flow diagrams** to visualize the food web structure of each model. The flow diagrams were built from the biomass and trophic levels (TL, as calculated by EwE) of each FG, and the direct trophic interactions among them. The TL identifies the position of organisms within food webs by identifying the source of energy for each organism, and it is calculated by assigning primary producers and detritus a TL of 1 (e.g. phytoplankton), and consumers to a TL of 1, plus the average TL of their prey weighted by their proportion in weight in the predator's diet (Christensen 1996).

We extracted **system indicators** related to the structural properties of the ecosystem informing about the status of maturity and complexity (Christensen 1995). These indicators assess the state the ecosystem and included the Total System Throughput (TST, $t \cdot km^{-2} \cdot year^{-1}$), the sum of all flows in the model (consumption, export, respiration and flow to detritus) and considered an overall measure of the “ecological size” of the system (Finn 1976), the Finn’s Cycling Index (FCI, %), the fraction of the ecosystem’s throughput that is recycled (Finn 1976), and the Average Path Length (APL), defined as the average number of groups that flows passes through and is an indicator of stress (Christensen 1995). Several additional indicators were selected because of their robustness in front of models comparison (Heymans et al. 2014): the ratios of consumption (Q), export (Ex) and production (P).

In addition, several **ecological indicators** were computed following a standardized procedure (Coll & Steenbeek 2017). These indicators were divided in 5 groups:

Biomass-based indicators: These indicators are calculated from the biomass of components included in the food-web model. Species biomass data are considered basic information to evaluate effectiveness in marine protected areas (Micheli 2004). Indicators included were total biomass (TB, $t \cdot km^{-2} \cdot year^{-1}$), biomass of commercial species (CB, $t \cdot km^{-2} \cdot year^{-1}$), biomass of fish species (FB, $t \cdot km^{-2} \cdot year^{-1}$), and Kempton Q diversity index (KI).

Catch-based indicators: These indicators are based on catch and discard species data in the food web. They can give an idea on the potential effect on adjacent fisheries through spill over of exploited fishes from protected areas (McClanahan & Mangi 2000). Indicators included were: total catch (TC $t \cdot km^{-2} \cdot year^{-1}$), total discarded catch (TD, $t \cdot km^{-2} \cdot year^{-1}$), trophic level of the catch (TLC), mean length of fish in the catch (MLC, cm) and mean life span of fish in the catch (MLC, year).

Trophic-based indicators: These indicators reflect the trophic level (TL) for different groups of the food web. TLs are calculated by assigning producers and detritus to trophic level 1, and consumers to a trophic level of 1 plus the average trophic level of their prey, weighted by their proportion in weight in the predator's diet (Christensen 1996, 2000). Trophic level may indicate ecosystem “health” because it reflects fishing pressure due to removal of predators (Christensen & Walters 2004). Indicators included were: TL of the community (TLc), TL of the community including organisms with $TL \geq 2$ (TL2), TL of the community including organisms with $TL \geq 3.25$ (TL3.25) and TL of the community including organisms with $TL \geq 4$ (TL4).

Species-based and size-based indicators: These indicators are based on species traits and conservation status. Increase in species traits such as mean length could be a direct effect of marine protected areas (Claudet et al. 2006). Indicators included were: the Intrinsic vulnerability index of catch (VI), biomass of IUCN-endangered species in the community (ES, $t \cdot km^{-2} \cdot year^{-1}$), mean length of fish in the community (ML, cm) and mean life span of fish community (MLS, year).

In addition, we computed the **Mixed Trophic Impact analysis (MTI)** to quantify direct and indirect trophic interactions among functional groups (Ulanowicz & Puccia 1990). This analysis quantifies the direct and indirect impacts that a hypothetical increase in the biomass of one functional group

would have on the biomasses of all the other functional groups, including the fishing fleets. The MTI for living groups is calculated by constructing an $n \times n$ matrix, and quantifying each interaction between the impacting group (j) and the impacted group (i) is:

$$MTI_{ji} = DC_{ji} - FC_{ij}, \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where DC_{ji} is the diet composition term expressing how much i contributes to the diet of j , and FC_{ij} is a host composition term giving the proportion of the predation on j that is due to i as a predator.

To identify the keystone species within the ecosystem, we used the **keystone index (KS)** using three different methods. A keystone species is a species that shows relatively low biomass but has a relatively important role in the ecosystem (Power et al., 1996). We used the indices compiled inside the Ecopath software: (1) the Power keystone indicator (Power et al. 1996) (KSp) and (2) Libralato's keystone indicator (Libralato et al. 2006) (KSl), which are based on a measure of trophic impact derived from the MTI analysis, and a quantitative measure of biomass; and (3) Valls (Valls et al. 2015) KSv) keystone index, in which the biomass component is based on a descending ranking of the biomass. These indices are calculated as:

$$KSp_i = \varepsilon_i \frac{1}{p_i} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

$$KSl_i = \log[\varepsilon_i(1 - p_i)] \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

$$KSv_i = \log[IC_i \cdot BC_i] \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

where ε_i represents the RTI; p_i is the contribution of the group i to the total biomass in the food-web; IC_i is a component estimating the trophic impact of the group i ; BC_i is a component estimating the biomass of the group i .

Evaluating the role of local MPAs and MUs: To evaluate the differences among the three local studied MPAs and the FRA areas, results from ecological indicators and keystone species were compared with the same MUs of different MPAs, between MPAs, and between FRA models before and after the establishment of the FRAs. For instance, direct comparison of MPAs across the three MPAs allowed us to capture the differences in their effects despite identical levels of protection. A multiple comparison procedure was explored for the three MUs to test the theory which suggests that reserve effects extend beyond FPA boundaries as a result of spill-over (Gell & Roberts 2003).

In order to determine the role of MUs in the functioning of the MPAs, results from ecological indicators (except catch-based indicators) and keystone species were compared across three MUs within a MPA. This analogy among MUs ecological indicators served to capture shifts in ecosystem functioning and structure due to proximity of different levels of protection. To compare the effects of the establishment of the FRA areas, we used the ecological models fitted to data for both GoL FRA and ZTB Argentario documented in *deliverable 4.3* to extract an Ecopath model for the year 2016 of the fitting procedure. This extracted model was analysed in the same manner as the originally created model that represented the period before the establishment of fisheries management measures in both areas.

Analyses of professional and recreational fisheries in MPA models: To evaluate the impact of fisheries, catch-based indicators were examined between PPAs and UPAs of the three MPAs, and between different models (FRAs, sub-regional and regional model). In addition, the Mixed Trophic Impact analysis results of the different fishing fleets were examined to quantify the direct and indirect

impact of each fleet on the functional groups of the ecosystems, any inter-fleet competitions, and fishing trade-offs. For the models of the MPAs and MUs we only included artisanal and recreational fisheries. The FRA, sub-regional and regional models included not only artisanal and recreational fisheries, but also other fisheries such as professional larger-scale fisheries (bottom trawling, midwater trawling, purse seines and longlining).

Results

Local models: MUs and MPAs

Cerbère-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands MUs

The final food-web structure of Cerbère-Banyuls MPA MU contained 64 functional groups (2 marine mammals, 3 seabirds, 1 sea turtle, 8 pelagic fish, 25 demersal fish, 3 cephalopods, 14 invertebrates, 2 primary producers, 2 zooplankton, 2 phytoplankton and 2 detritus), and 66 functional groups for Cap de Creus MPA and Medes Islands MPAs (2 marine mammals, 3 seabirds, 1 sea turtle, 8 pelagic fish, 25 demersal fish, 3 cephalopods, 14 invertebrates, 4 primary producers, 2 zooplankton, 2 phytoplankton and 2 detritus) (Figure 10 and Tables in Supplementary Material). Except in the case of FPA, which do not have discards because all fishing extractions are forbidden, food-web structures of each MU in the same MPA were identical.

Figure 10. Flow diagram of fully protected areas (FPAs), partially protected areas (PPAs) and Unprotected areas (UPAs) of (a) Cerbère-Banyuls MPA, (b) Cap de Creus, and (c) Medes Islands MPA models, organized by Trophic Levels (y-axis). The size of each circle is proportional to the biomass of the functional group. The width of connecting lines is proportional to the magnitude of their flows. Primary producers and detritus are represented in blue and top predators in orange.

The pedigree index values of MU models showed similar values between the MUs (Figure 11), ranging from 0.41 to 0.52. The highest pedigree values were obtained for Cèrbère-Banyuls, and regarding MUs, FPAs obtained slightly lower pedigree index than the other MUs.

Figure 11. Pedigree index values of three MUs models for each MPA.

Ecological indicators of the MUs MPA models

Overall, biomass-based indicators displayed similar patterns between MUs (Figure 12), with the highest biomass values found for Cèrbère-Banyuls, then Medes Islands and finally Cap de Creus. Conversely, KI decreased from Cap de Creus to Medes Islands and then Cèrbère-Banyuls, which showed the lowest KI value. Within MUs, the FPAs showed the highest values in terms of total and fish biomass, and they were followed by PPA in all MPAs. In Cap de Creus we observed similar values among MUs for both indicators.

Figure 12. Biomass-based indicators of three MUs (FPA: fully protected area; PPA: partially protected area; UPA: unprotected area) models for each MPA (Banyuls, Medes, and Cap de Creus).

Trophic-based indicators revealed that in general the TL of the community and TL2 was higher for Cèrbere-Banyuls, followed by Medes Islands, while Cap de Creus showed lower levels (Figure 13). Cèrbere-Banyuls and Medes Islands displayed similar values for TL 325 and TL 4, and Cap de Creus obtained higher variance among these indicators. Specifically, Cap de Creus showed the highest TL 325 values and the lowest TL 4 value. Within MUs, most trophic-based indicators showed the highest values for FPAs followed by PPAs and UPAs showed the lowest results. On the contrary, the FPA achieved the lowest values in Cap de Creus, with the exception of TL 3.25.

Flows-based indicators showed differences between MPA. Cèrbere-Banyuls showed the highest values for Q/TST, TST, FCI and APL, while the lowest values for Ex/TST and P/TST (Figure 14). Inversely Cap de Creus showed the lowest values for Q/TST, whilst the highest values for Ex/TST and P/TST. Medes Islands values were located between these two MPAs. Considering MUs values, flows-based results revealed higher values for FPAs followed by PPAs in most of the flows-based indicators. As an exception, Ex/TST and P/TST were higher for UPAs and lower for FPAs.

Results from species and size-based indicators (Figure 15) pointed out that Cèrbere-Banyuls had the highest values for IUCN species B and was followed to Medes Islands. Regarding ML and MLS, the highest values were also obtained for Banyuls, followed by Cap de Creus and then Medes Islands. IUCN species biomass, ML and MLS were higher for FPAs, except in Cap de Creus, where PPA and FPA acquired similar results.

Considering catch data, total catch and discards data showed similar values between Cap de Creus and Medes Islands, while Cèrbere-Banyuls showed the lowest values (Figure 16). IV values were similar for Cap de Creus and Cèrbere-Banyuls, and the lowest IV values were found for Medes Islands. TLc were higher for Cèrbere-Banyuls and Cap de Creus and lower for Medes Islands, and these results are in line with MLSc results (Figure 15). Also, Cèrbere-Banyuls obtained the highest value for MLc while Cap de Creus got the lowest values. TC and discards exhibited higher values for PPAs than UPAs. IV indexes were higher for PPAs than UPAs except for Cèrbere-Banyuls. TLc values were similar between PPA and UPA in Cap de Creus and Medes Islands, while it was higher for PPA in Cèrbere-Banyuls. ML and MLS results evidenced similar values between MUs for Medes Islands, while PPA obtained higher values in Cap de Creus and lower in Cèrbere-Banyuls.

Keystone species of the MUs MPA models

All keystone indices (Figure 17) for the nine models identified the same groups as keystone species: Groupers, Other commercial medium demersal fish, Common dentex, and Labridae & Serranidae. Particularly, Groupers obtained the highest relative total impact. These results confirmed that these functional groups play an important ecological role in Mediterranean coastal protected ecosystems.

Keystoneness indices showed different patterns among MUs and MPAs. Medes Islands models obtained the highest number of keystone species followed by Cèrbere-Banyuls (Figure 17). Specifically, the largest differences between MPAs were found in KS_P and KS_V where Medes Islands obtained the highest keystoneness index values except for the FPAs located in the Cap de Creus area, which showed higher keystoneness index values. Within MPAs, the largest differences between MUs were displayed in KS_L and KS_P . While FPAs obtained the highest keystoneness index values in KS_L , KS_P highlighted UPAs as the MU with the highest keystoneness index values.

Figure 17. Keystone Index analysis of three MU (FPA: fully protected area; PPA: partially protected area; UPA: unprotected area) models for each MPA (Cèrbere-Banyuls, Medes Islands, and Cap de Creus). The acronyms identify the functional group with highest keystoneness index and relative total impact. (GRO – Groupers; CDE – Common dentex; OCD – Other commercial medium demersal fishes; L&S – Labridae and Serranidae).

Mixed trophic impact analysis of the MUs MPA models

The MTI analysis based on the recreational fisheries (Figure 18) revealed that results of recreational fisheries impacting the rest of the functional groups in the ecosystem were clearly higher than impacted values of groups to recreational fisheries (between -0.86 and 0.84 and -0.15 and 0.26, respectively). The highest impacting and impacted values were found for PPA in Cap de Creus, with some exceptions for some groups, where impacted values were higher for PPA in Cèrbere-Banyuls (positively on Sparidae and negatively on Brown meagre, Common dentex and Groupers) and Medes Islands (positively on Common two-banded seabream and Red scorpionfish). Recreational fisheries impacted values were quite low (close to zero) for most groups except for Groupers and Sparidae in Cèrbere-Banyuls due to their higher catches and thus their importance to recreational fisheries.

Figure 18. Recreational impacting and impacted values of three MUs (PPA: partially protected area; UPA: unprotected area) models for each MPA (Cèrbere-Banyuls, Medes Islands and Cap de Creus).

In line with recreational fisheries impacting values, artisanal fisheries impacting results (Figure 19) indicated clearly higher and more fluctuating values than impacted values of groups to artisanal fisheries (ranging from -0.80 to 0.77 and -0.32 to 0.12, respectively). Generally, artisanal impact results did not evidence great differences between MUs. The highest artisanal fisheries impacting values were obtained in Cèrbere-Banyuls, with some exceptions for negative impacting values of some groups (Common pandora and Red mullet) in Cap de Creus. Artisanal fisheries impacted results displayed low values (close to zero), except for Groupers group which highly impacted on the artisanal fishery of PPA in Cap de Creus.

Figure 19. Artisanal impacting and impacted values of three MUs (PPA: partially protected area; UPA: unprotected area) models for each MPA (Cèrbere-Banyuls, Medes and Cap de Creus).

Cerbère-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands MPA models

The three MPAs Ecopath models included 64 (Cèrbere-Banyuls) and 67 (Cap de Creus and Medes Islands) functional groups, which ranked from TL 1 (primary producers) to TL 4.18 and 4.23 (functional group of bottlenose dolphins) in Cèrbere-Banyuls and Medes Islands, and TL 4.19 (Striped dolphins) in Cap de Creus (Table 1 and Figure 20 and Tables Supplementary Material).

When placing the fleets within the food web structure, the highest trophic position was observed for the recreational fleet in Medes Islands (with a TL = 4.61) and in Cap de Creus (TL = 4.54) and for the artisanal fleet in Cèrbere-Banyuls (TL = 4.42). The artisanal fisheries in Medes Islands (with TL 4.17) and in Cap de Creus (TL 4.30) and the recreational fisheries in Cèrbere-Banyuls (TL 4.16) showed the lowest positions.

System-based indicators of Cèrbere-Banyuls, Cap de Creus, and Medes Islands MPA models

The pedigree index of the models was average, ranging between 0.43 and 0.51, and similar to the values obtained for the MU models (Table 2). In general, several system-based indicators were higher in Cèrbere-Banyuls (57%), followed by Medes Islands (64%) and Cap de Creus (47%). This was the case for the sum of all consumption, of all respiratory flows, of all flows into detritus, of all production, Total system throughput, Total biomass (excluding detritus), and Shannon diversity index, in addition to the pedigree.

Table 2. System-based indicators of whole MPA and surrounding areas models of (a) Cèrbère-Banyuls MPA, (b) Cap de Creus and (c) Medes Islands.

Parameter	Banyuls	Creus	Medes	Units
Sum of all consumption	4920.14	2114.62	3797.24	t/km ² /year
Sum of all exports	88.67	583.16	51.34	t/km ² /year
Sum of all respiratory flows	2234.13	900.80	1738.03	t/km ² /year
Sum of all flows into detritus	2619.70	1814.71	2319.62	t/km ² /year
Total system throughput	9862.64	5413.28	7906.22	t/km ² /year
Sum of all production	2380.17	1802.63	2217.17	t/km ² /year
Mean trophic level of the catch	3.31	3.31	3.17	
Gross efficiency (catch/net p.p.)	0.00004	0.00017	0.00014	
Calculated total net primary production	1304.52	1300.81	1384.53	t/km ² /year
Total primary production/total respiration	0.58	1.44	0.80	
Net system production	-929.62	400.01	-353.50	t/km ² /year
Total primary production/total biomass	3.42	6.64	4.98	
Total biomass/total throughput	0.039	0.036	0.035	t/km ² /year
Total biomass (excluding detritus)	381.24	196.00	277.96	t/km ²
Total catch	0.05	0.22	0.19	t/km ² /year
Connectance Index	0.17	0.17	0.17	
System Omnivory Index	0.39	0.39	0.40	
Ecopath pedigree	0.51	0.43	0.44	
Shannon diversity index	2.58	2.48	2.58	

Ecological indicators of Cèrbère-Banyuls, Cap de Creus, and Medes Islands MPA models

The biomass-based indicators and the Shannon diversity index showed larger fish, commercial and pelagic biomass in Cèrbère-Banyuls, followed by Medes Islands and finally by Cap de Creus (Table 3) (Figure 21), with a contrary pattern for the Kemptons Q indicator. The trophic level indicators showed similar order of values as the biomass indicators, with larger values for Cèrbère-Banyuls, followed by Medes Islands and with lower values for Cap de Creus, with the exception of the TL community 4 (Figure 22). Comparison of size-based indicators of species in the catch to the metrics in the community show a selection of the targeted species towards larger and longer-lived species (Figure 23). The intrinsic vulnerabilities of the caught species to fishing is medium-low for all the areas and, on the contrary, there were larger catches in Cap de Creus and Medes Islands than in Cèrbère-Banyuls (Figure 22 and 23). Total catch and discards is larger in Cap de Creus and Medes (Figure 24).

Table 3. Ecological indicators of the whole MPA models of (a) Cerbère-Banyuls MPA, (b) Cap de Creus and (c) Medes Islands.

Indicator	Banyuls	Creus	Medes	Units	Description
Biomass-based					
Total B	1454.87	1122.80	1513.27	t/km2	Total biomass (B)
Commercial B	129.19	37.70	85.93	t/km2	Biomass (B) of commercial species
Fish B	127.21	33.04	79.33	t/km2	Biomass (B) of fish species
Invertebrates B	31.32	85.75	28.17	t/km2	Biomass (B) of invertebrate species
Invertebrates / Fish B	0.25	2.60	0.36		Biomass (B) of invertebrates over fish
Demersal B	47.48	159.33	25.70	t/km2	Biomass (B) of demersal species
Pelagic B	56.63	28.77	45.06	t/km2	Biomass (B) of pelagic species
Demersal / Pelagic B	0.84	5.54	0.57		Biomass (B) of demersal over pelagic species
Predatory B	0.03	0.03	0.03	t/km2	Biomass (B) of predatory organisms with trophic level ≥ 4
Kempton's Q	4.72	6.86	5.31		Kempton's diversity index (Q)
Shannon diversity	2.58	2.48	2.58		Shannon diversity index
Catch-based					
Total C	0.05	0.22	0.19	t/km2/year	Total catch (C)
Fish C	0.05	0.13	0.14	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of all fish species
Invertebrate C	0.00	0.08	0.01	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of all invertebrate species
Invertebrates / Fish C	0.04	0.63	0.08		Catch (C) of invertebrates over fish
Demersal C	0.03	0.10	0.10	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of demersal species
Pelagic C	0.02	0.05	0.04	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of pelagic species
Demersal / pelagic C	1.61	2.18	2.74		Catch (C) of demersal over pelagic species
Predatory C	0.000	0.002	0.001	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of predatory organisms with trophic level ≥ 4
Discards	0.00	0.02	0.01	t/km2/year	Total discarded catch
Trophic-based					
TL catch	3.31	3.31	3.17		Trophic level (TL) of the catch
MTI	3.67	3.46	3.56		Marine trophic index or trophic level (TL) of the catch including organisms with TL ≥ 3.25
TL community	1.32	1.14	1.20		Trophic level (TL) of the community
TL community 2	2.37	2.35	2.30		Trophic level (TL) of the community including organisms with TL ≥ 2
TL community 3.25	3.63	3.50	3.48		Trophic level (TL) of the community including organisms with TL ≥ 3.25
TL community 4	4.17	4.16	4.19		Trophic level (TL) of the community including organisms with TL ≥ 4
Species-based					
Intrinsic Vul. Index	53.07	53.01	49.41		Intrinsic Vulnerability Index of the catch
Endemics B	22.43	53.80	14.90	t/km2	Biomass (B) of endemic species in the community
Endemics C	0.000	0.000	0.000	t/km2/year	Endemic species in the catch (C)
IUCN species B	20.47	4.20	3.10	t/km2	Biomass (B) of IUCN-endangered species in the community
IUCN species C	0.00	0.01	0.01	t/km2/year	Proportion of IUCN-endangered species in the catch (C)
Mammals, birds & reptiles B	0.04	0.04	0.04	t/km2	Biomass (B) of marine mammals, seabirds and reptiles
Mammals, birds & reptiles C	0	0	0	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of marine mammals, seabirds and reptiles
Size-based					
ML of fish community	32.38	28.29	26.44	cm	Mean length (ML) of fish in the community
ML of fish C	43.04	33.29	29.40	cm	Mean length (ML) of fish in the catch (C)
MW of fish community	0.54	0.40	0.32	kg	Mean weight (MW) of the fish in the community
MW of fish C	2.50	0.93	0.61	kg	Mean weight (MW) of fish in the catch (C)
MLS of fish community	17.08	19.57	15.55	y	Mean life span (MLS) of fish in the community
MLS of fish C	17.57	18.11	15.90	y	Mean life span (MLS) of fish the catch (C)

Figure 21. Biomass-based indicators of the whole MPA models of Cerbère-Banyuls MPA, Cap de Creus, and Medes Islands.

Figure 22. Trophic-based indicators of the whole MPA models of Cerbère-Banyuls MPA, Cap de Creus, and Medes Islands.

Figure 23. Species and size-base indicators of the whole MPA models of Cerbère-Banyuls MPA, Cap de Creus, and Medes Islands.

Figure 24. Catch-base indicators of the whole MPA models of Cerbère-Banyuls MPA, Cap de Creus, and Medes Islands.

Keystone species of Cèrbere-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands MPA models

The keystone indicators allowed us to identify those species with relative larger impacts in the ecosystem considering their relative low biomass. Overall, Groupers, Common dentex and Other commercial medium demersal fishes were highlighted as the functional groups with largest keystone index, especially when using KS3 of Valls et al. 2015 (Figure 25), in agreement with results from the individual management units (Figure 17 and Tables in Supplementary Material).

Mixed trophic impact analysis of Cèrbere-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands MPA models

The mixed trophic impact (MTI) analysis applied to the fleet groups of the three MPAs allowed us to 1) identify inter-fleet impacts and trade-offs, and 2) the impacts of fleets on the living functional groups of the ecosystem (Figure 26). The analysis highlighted that each fleet had a negative impact on itself due to self-competition for resources. In Cap de Creus and Medes Islands, the recreational fisheries had a positive impact on artisanal fisheries, which was not observed in Cèrbere-Banyuls. Therefore, we identified complex trade-offs between the main fleet sectors operating in the study area.

The MTI analyses also highlighted larger impacts by trawl on several functional groups, with a mix of strong positive or negative impacts on main targeted species and competitors or prey of those species (Figure 26). The impacts of recreational fisheries were very prominent in Cap de Creus, followed by Medes, while the impacts in Cèrbere-Banyuls were much less. On the contrary, in Cèrbere-Banyuls the impact of artisanal fisheries was larger compared to that of recreational fisheries.

Figure 26. The Mixed Trophic Impact analysis of a) Cèrbere-Banyuls, b) Cap de Creus and c) Medes Islands MPA models based on the impacts of the fishing fleets on the functional groups. Negative impacts are printed in red, while positive impacts are printed in blue.

FRA models of the Gulf of Lions and ZTB Argentario

The two Ecopath models of Gulf of Lions and ZTB Argentario included 71 (Gulf of Lions) and 68 (ZTB Argentario) functional groups, which ranked from TL 1 to 4.63 (pelagic sharks) in ZTB Argentario and to TL 4.43 (bottlenose dolphins) in Gulf of Lions (Figure 27 and Tables in Supplementary Material).

When placing the fleets within the food web structure, the highest trophic position was observed for the longline and midwater trawling fisheries in Gulf of Lions (with a TL = 4.79 and TL = 4.64, respectively). The bottom trawling both in ZTB Argentario and in Gulf of Lions had similar TL of 4.3.

System-based indicators of Gulf of Lions and ZTB Argentario models

The pedigree index of the two models was average, a bit higher for the Gulf of Lions than for the Argentario (Table 4). In general, several system-based indicators were higher in Gulf of Lions (79%), which corresponded to a larger study area and larger ecosystem size in terms of energy fluxes. The catch indicators showed a similar impact and position of fisheries, with a slight higher numbers for the Gulf of Lions FRA.

Table 4. System-based indicators of the Gulf of Lions FRA and ZTB Argentario FRA models.

Parameter	GoL	Argentario	Units
Sum of all consumption	631.47	297.60	t/km ² /year
Sum of all exports	1031.62	807.40	t/km ² /year
Sum of all respiratory flows	186.33	124.88	t/km ² /year
Sum of all flows into detritus	1150.79	973.65	t/km ² /year
Total system throughput	3000.22	2203.53	t/km ² /year
Sum of all production	1423.28	1005.20	t/km ² /year
Mean trophic level of the catch	3.42	3.31	
Gross efficiency (catch/net p.p.)	0.00044	0.00036	
Calculated total net primary production	1217.96	924.59	t/km ² /year
Total primary production/total respiration	6.54	7.40	
Net system production	1031.62	799.71	t/km ² /year
Total primary production/total biomass	50.82	38.03	
Total biomass/total throughput	0.008	0.011	t/km ² /year
Total biomass (excluding detritus)	23.97	24.31	t/km ²
Total catch	0.53	0.33	t/km ² /year
Connectance Index	0.16	0.15	
System Omnivory Index	0.17	0.25	
Ecopath pedigree	0.64	0.42	
Shannon diversity index	2.42	1.88	

Ecological indicators of Gulf of Lions and ZTB Argentario models

The biomass-based indicators showed larger fish biomass, pelagic biomass and commercial biomass in the Gulf of Lions, and larger invertebrates and demersal biomass in ZTB Argentario, partially reflecting the nature of both sites (Table 5), with a contrasting pattern for the Kemptons Q and Shannon diversity indicators. The trophic level indicators also showed larger values in Gulf of Lions, with the exception of the TL community and TL community 3.25. The intrinsic vulnerabilities to fishing of the caught species was medium-low for both areas. Larger biomass and catch of endemic and IUCN classified species were encountered in the Gulf of Lions. The size-based indicators of species in the catch in comparison to the metrics in the community showed a selection of the targeted species on both areas. Catch indicators were slightly higher in the Gulf of Lions in agreement with biomass results with larger catches based on invertebrates in Argentario FRA.

Table 5. Ecological indicators of the Gulf of Lions FRA and ZTB Argentario FRA models.

Indicator	GoL	Argentario	Units	Description
Biomass-based				
Total B	135.07	84.87	t/km2	Total biomass (B)
Commercial B	5.56	4.01	t/km2	Biomass (B) of commercial species
Fish B	5.22	2.94	t/km2	Biomass (B) of fish species
Invertebrates B	0.64	1.33	t/km2	Biomass (B) of invertebrate species
Invertebrates / Fish B	0.12	0.45		Biomass (B) of invertebrates over fish
Demersal B	1.07	1.46	t/km2	Biomass (B) of demersal species
Pelagic B	4.48	2.50	t/km2	Biomass (B) of pelagic species
Demersal / Pelagic B	0.24	0.58		Biomass (B) of demersal over pelagic species
Predatory B	0.36	0.21	t/km2	Biomass (B) of predatory organisms with trophic level ≥ 4
Kempton's Q	9.11	11.91		Kempton's diversity index (Q)
Shannon diversity	2.42	1.88		Shannon diversity index
Catch-based				
Total C	0.53	0.33	t/km2/year	Total catch (C)
Fish C	0.49	0.24	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of all fish species
Invertebrate C	0.04	0.08	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of all invertebrate species
Invertebrates / Fish C	0.09	0.31		Catch (C) of invertebrates over fish
Demersal C	0.16	0.11	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of demersal species
Pelagic C	0.37	0.19	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of pelagic species
Demersal / pelagic C	0.43	0.55		Catch (C) of demersal over pelagic species
Predatory C	0.081	0.031	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of predatory organisms with trophic level ≥ 4
Discards	0.10	0.02	t/km2/year	Total discarded catch
Trophic-based				
TL catch	3.42	3.31		Trophic level (TL) of the catch
MTI	3.72	3.61		Marine trophic index or trophic level (TL) of the catch including organisms with TL ≥ 3.25
TL community	1.18	1.27		Trophic level (TL) of the community
TL community 2	2.59	2.23		Trophic level (TL) of the community including organisms with TL ≥ 2
TL community 3.25	3.64	3.68		Trophic level (TL) of the community including organisms with TL ≥ 3.25
TL community 4	4.23	4.10		Trophic level (TL) of the community including organisms with TL ≥ 4
Species-based				
Intrinsic Vul. Index	40.88	41.36		Intrinsic Vulnerability Index of the catch
Endemics B	0.14	0.10	t/km2	Biomass (B) of endemic species in the community
Endemics C	0.000	0.000	t/km2/year	Endemic species in the catch (C)
IUCN species B	0.88	0.35	t/km2	Biomass (B) of IUCN-endangered species in the community
IUCN species C	0.02	0.01	t/km2/year	Proportion of IUCN-endangered species in the catch (C)
Mammals, birds & reptiles B	0.03	0.03	t/km2	Biomass (B) of marine mammals, seabirds and reptiles
Size-based				
ML of fish community	29.38	61.28	cm	Mean length (ML) of fish in the community
ML of fish C	29.92	45.43	cm	Mean length (ML) of fish in the catch (C)
MW of fish community	4.79	7.79	kg	Mean weight (MW) of the fish in the community
MW of fish C	0.74	2.14	kg	Mean weight (MW) of fish in the catch (C)
MLS of fish community	12.21	9.93	y	Mean life span (MLS) of fish in the community
MLS of fish C	12.12	9.15	y	Mean life span (MLS) of fish the catch (C)

Keystone species of Gulf of Lions and ZTB Argentario models

Overall, Anglerfish, Other commercial medium demersal fish and bottlenose dolphins were high in both models when using KS3 of Valls et al. 2015 (Figure 28 and Tables in Supplementary Material). In addition, in the case of the Gulf of Lions, Rays and skates, Sparidae, Common Pandora, Benthopelagic cephalopods and Bluefin tuna also ranked the highest, while in the ZTB Argentario we also identified Pelagic sharks, Norway lobster, Deep-water rose shrimp, Loggerhead turtles and Other commercial decapods as important groups. When using the other two indicators (Libralato et al. 2006 and Power et al 1996) other more abundant species such as zooplankton or rare species such as seabirds were also identified as potential keystone species (Tables in Supplementary Material).

Mixed trophic impact analysis of Gulf of Lions and ZTB Argentario models

The mixed trophic impact (MTI) analysis applied to the fleet groups of the two FRAs highlighted that each fleet had a negative impact on itself due to self-competition for resources in the Gulf of Lions and also with the others, suggesting high competition for resources (Figure 29).

The MTI analyses highlighted larger impacts by midwater and bottom trawl on several functional groups, with a mix of strong negative and positive impacts on main targeted species and competitors or prey of those species (Figure 29). In general, there was larger negative impacts on fish species, and larger positive impacts on invertebrate species and fish species that were not the primary target of the fisheries.

Figure 29. The Mixed Trophic Impact analyses of the Gulf of Lions FRA and ZTB Argentario FRA models based on the impacts of the fishing fleets on the functional groups. Negative impacts are printed in red, while positive impacts are printed in blue.

Ecological indicators before and after the establishment of the of Gulf of Lions FRA

After the implementation of the GoL FRA, fish, demersal community, commercial organisms, invertebrates and predatory fish biomass decreased (Figure 30). Controversially, total biomass increased mainly due to accumulation of detritus. Trophic level-based indicators decreased around 0.3 units except for the TL community 4 which increased after the establishment (Figure 31). Catch-based indicators decreased from 2008 to 2016 (Figure 32). Both models highlighted the same functional groups, highlighting Anglerfish, which lost keystone index value after the implementation of the GoL FRA (Figure 33).

Figure 30. Biomass-based indicators of the GoL FRA before and after the establishment.

Figure 31. Trophic level-based indicators of the GoL FRA before and after the establishment.

Figure 32. Catch-based indicators of the GoL FRA before and after the establishment.

Figure 33. Keystone Index analysis of the Gulf of Lions FRA before and after the establishment. Anglerfish (21), Macrozooplankton (66) and Meso and microzooplankton (67).

Ecological indicators before and after the establishment of the ZTB Argentario

After the implementation of the ZTB Argentario, all biomass-based indicators decreased (Figure 34). Trophic level-based indicators decreased with the exception of TL community (Figure 35). TL of the catch increased after the establishment, but the rest of the catch-based indicators decreased (Figure 36). Both models highlighted pelagic sharks, European sardine, anglerfish and Macrozooplankton as keystone species but they all showed a decline on their keystone index value after the establishment of the ZTB (Figure 37).

Figure 34. Biomass-based indicators of the ZTB Argentario before and after the establishment.

Figure 35. Trophic level-based indicators of the ZTB Argentario before and after the establishment.

Figure 36. Catch-based indicators of the ZTB Argentario before and after the establishment.

Sub-regional model of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea

The sub-regional Northwestern Mediterranean Sea model included 67 functional groups, which ranked from TL 1 (primary producers) to TL 4.17 (functional group of bottlenose dolphins) (Figure 38 and Table in Supplementary Material). When placing the fleets within the food web structure, the highest trophic position was observed for the artisanal fleet (with a TL = 4.42) and trawling (TL = 4.41). Recreational fisheries followed (TL = 4.34) and purse seine showed the lowest positions (TL = 4.04).

System-based indicators of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea model

The pedigree index of the model was higher (pedigree index = 0.721) than for the local food web models (Table 6), as better data were available for the area of the sub-regional model (e.g., scientific surveys, and national and regional statistics) than for the smaller coastal areas represented by the local models.

Table 6. System-based indicators of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea model (2010).

Parameter	Value	Units
Sum of all consumption	576.74	t/km ² /year
Sum of all exports	909.99	t/km ² /year
Sum of all respiratory flows	204.91	t/km ² /year
Sum of all flows into detritus	1162.16	t/km ² /year
Total system throughput	2853.80	t/km ² /year
Sum of all production	1276.20	t/km ² /year
Mean trophic level of the catch	3.21	
Gross efficiency (catch/net p.p.)	0.001	
Calculated total net primary production	1114.40	t/km ² /year
Total primary production/total respiration	5.44	
Net system production	909.49	t/km ² /year
Total primary production/total biomass	28.65	
Total biomass/total throughput	0.01	t/km ² /year
Total biomass (excluding detritus)	38.90	t/km ²
Total catch	0.67	t/km ² /year
Connectance Index	0.17	
System Omnivory Index	0.21	
Ecopath pedigree	0.72	
Shannon diversity index	2.80	

Ecological indicators of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea model

The biomass-based indicators showed a larger portion of invertebrates in comparison with fish in the ecosystem of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea, and a similar ration of demersal and pelagic biomass (Table 7) (Figure 39). On the contrary, a larger portion of the catch came from the pelagic environment and from fish organisms, providing evidence for a larger impact of fisheries onto pelagic fish communities (Figure 40). The trophic level of the community showed low values, while the trophic level of the catch illustrated that the organisms targeted by the fishery were in low trophic positions (such as invertebrates and first order carnivore fishes) (Figure 41). This was also highlighted by the overall low levels of the intrinsic vulnerabilities to fishing of caught species (Figure 42) and the size-based indicators of species in the catch in comparison to the metrics of the community (Figure 43).

Table 7. Ecological indicators of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea model (2010).

Indicator	Value	Units	Description
Biomass-based			
Total B	868.31	t/km ²	Total biomass (B)
Commercial B	9.31	t/km ²	Biomass (B) of commercial species
Fish B	5.25	t/km ²	Biomass (B) of fish species
Invertebrates B	8.83	t/km ²	Biomass (B) of invertebrate species
Invertebrates / Fish B	1.68		Biomass (B) of invertebrates over fish
Demersal B	3.47	t/km ²	Biomass (B) of demersal species
Pelagic B	3.32	t/km ²	Biomass (B) of pelagic species
Demersal / Pelagic B	1.04		Biomass (B) of demersal over pelagic species
Predatory B	0.14	t/km ²	Biomass (B) of predatory organisms with trophic level ≥ 4
Kempton's Q	10.05		Kempton's diversity index (Q)
Shannon diversity	2.80		Shannon diversity index
Catch-based			
Total C	0.67	t/km ² /year	Total catch (C)
Fish C	0.56	t/km ² /year	Catch (C) of all fish species
Invertebrate C	0.07	t/km ² /year	Catch (C) of all invertebrate species
Invertebrates / Fish C	0.13		Catch (C) of invertebrates over fish
Demersal C	0.18	t/km ² /year	Catch (C) of demersal species
Pelagic C	0.44	t/km ² /year	Catch (C) of pelagic species
Demersal / pelagic C	0.42		Catch (C) of demersal over pelagic species
Predatory C	0.002	t/km ² /year	Catch (C) of predatory organisms with trophic level ≥ 4
Discards	0.10	t/km ² /year	Total discarded catch
Trophic-based			
TL catch	3.21		Trophic level (TL) of the catch
MTI	3.65		Marine trophic index or trophic level (TL) of the catch including organisms with TL ≥ 3.25
TL community	1.03		Trophic level (TL) of the community
TL community 2	2.37		Trophic level (TL) of the community including organisms with TL ≥ 2
TL community 3.25	3.56		Trophic level (TL) of the community including organisms with TL ≥ 3.25
TL community 4	4.11		Trophic level (TL) of the community including organisms with TL ≥ 4
Species-based			
Intrinsic Vul. Index	36.29		Intrinsic Vulnerability Index of the catch
Endemics B	3.95	t/km ²	Biomass (B) of endemic species in the community
Endemics C	0.000	t/km ² /year	Endemic species in the catch (C)
IUCN species B	0.55	t/km ²	Biomass (B) of IUCN-endangered species in the community
IUCN species C	0.03	t/km ² /year	Proportion of IUCN-endangered species in the catch (C)
Mammals, birds & reptiles B	0.04	t/km ²	Biomass (B) of marine mammals, seabirds and reptiles
Mammals, birds & reptiles C	0	t/km ² /year	Catch (C) of marine mammals, seabirds and reptiles
Size-based			
ML of fish community	26.76	cm	Mean length (ML) of fish in the community
ML of fish C	25.23	cm	Mean length (ML) of fish in the catch (C)
MW of fish community	3.26	kg	Mean weight (MW) of the fish in the community
MW of fish C	0.60	kg	Mean weight (MW) of fish in the catch (C)
MLS of fish community	16.03	y	Mean life span (MLS) of fish in the community
MLS of fish C	10.34	y	Mean life span (MLS) of fish the catch (C)

Keystone species of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea model

Overall, Anglerfish, Other commercial medium demersal fish, Groupers, Common dentex and European hake were highlighted as the functional groups with largest keystone-ness, especially when using KS3 of Valls et al. 2015 (Figure 44). In addition, Bottlenose dolphins, Striped dolphins, Bluefin tuna, Mackerels, Other medium pelagic fishes, European conger, Other commercial medium demersal fish and Benthopelagic cephalopods were identified in high positions of the keystone-ness importance.

When using the indicator by Libralato et al (2012), other groups with larger biomasses were identified (such as mesozooplankton), while when using Power et al. (2006) rare species with low levels of biomass in the ecosystem were highlighted (such as seabirds) (Table in Supplementary Material).

Mixed trophic impact analysis of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea model

The mixed trophic impact (MTI) analysis applied to the fleet groups of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea model allowed us to 1) identify the impacts of fleets between them (trade-offs) and 2) the impacts of fleets on the living functional groups of the ecosystem (Figure 45). The analysis highlighted that each fleet had a negative impact on itself due to self-competition for resources. In addition, bottom trawl a positive impact on purse seine and a negative impact on artisanal fisheries. Purse seine had a negative impact on artisanal fisheries and a positive impact on the recreational fisheries. The artisanal fisheries had a negative impact on the recreational and trawl, and a slight positive impact on the purse seine. The recreational fisheries showed mainly a positive interaction with the artisanal fisheries. Therefore, we identified complex trade-offs between the main fleet sectors operating in the study area, while there is a high competition between them in terms of targeted commercial species.

The MTI also analyses highlighted larger impacts by trawl on several functional groups, with negative impacts dominating (such as in demersal sharks and fishes, and large pelagic fishes) (Figure 45). Due to depletion of competitors or predators, some groups were positively impacted by trawling. These groups included Torpedos, White seabream and Common-two branded seabream, and the Gelatinous groups (both jellyfishes and salps). The purse seine showed mainly negative impacts on target species, with the exception of Horse mackerels and Other small pelagic fish, in addition to showing positive impacts to gelatinous groups, too (both jellyfishes and salps). The artisanal and recreational fisheries showed less widespread impacts, but larger negative impacts on their targeted species (such as Groupers and Swordfish).

Figure 45. The Mixed Trophic Impact analyses of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea model based on the impacts of the fishing fleets on the functional groups. Negative impacts are printed in red, while positive impacts are printed in blue.

Regional model of the Western Mediterranean Sea

The regional Western Mediterranean Sea model included 90 functional groups, which ranked from TL 1 (primary producers) to TL 4.73 (functional group of pelagic sharks) (Figure 46 and Table in Supplementary Material). When placing the fleets within the food web, the highest trophic position was observed for the longline fleet (with a TL = 4.99) and recreational fisheries (TL = 4.68). Bottom trawlers followed (TL = 4.34), while purse seiners & midwater trawlers and artisanal fisheries showed the lowest positions (TL = 4.21 and 4.01, respectively).

Figure 46. Flow diagram representing the Western Mediterranean Sea food web model organized by Trophic Levels (y-axis). The size of each circle is proportional to the biomass of the functional group. The wideness of the connecting lines is proportional to the magnitude of their flows. Functional groups are organized by pelagic (left), demersal (centre) and benthic (right) positions in the figure.

The pedigree index of the model (pedigree index = 0.47) was lower than the sub-regional model and of the same order of magnitude of the local food-web models developed before (Table 8); information available for the Western Mediterranean Sea came from different sources with varying degrees of confidence, including lower-confidence FAO databases for non-EU Mediterranean countries.

System-based indicators of the Western Mediterranean Sea model

Compared to the sub-regional model (Table 6), the Western Mediterranean Sea model showed the largest ecosystem size, with highest estimates for all flows. Some features related to the functioning of the ecosystem such as the System Omnivory index, the Connectance Index and the total primary production / total respiration were similar to the sub-regional model, and some features of the fishery footprint, such as the TL catch and the total catch per km² were of similar dimensions, too (Table 8). However, the Shannon diversity index, total biomass per km², and the gross efficiency index were very different between the two models, as these models represent very different geographic scales. In addition, the sub-regional model represents a coastal shelf area, while the Western Model is predominantly dominated by the pelagic and deep-sea environment.

Table 8. System-based indicators of the Western Mediterranean Sea model (2010).

Parameter	Value	Units
Sum of all consumption	31837.15	t/km ² /year
Sum of all exports	49400.58	t/km ² /year
Sum of all respiratory flows	11997.44	t/km ² /year
Sum of all flows into detritus	56611.07	t/km ² /year
Total system throughput	149846.30	t/km ² /year
Sum of all production	74870.07	t/km ² /year
Mean trophic level of the catch	3.31	
Gross efficiency (catch/net p.p.)	0.00001	
Calculated total net primary production	61397.79	t/km ² /year
Total primary production/total respiration	5.12	
Net system production	49400.35	t/km ² /year
Total primary production/total biomass	90.88	
Total biomass/total throughput	0.005	t/km ² /year
Total biomass (excluding detritus)	675.59	t/km ²
Total catch	0.61	t/km ² /year
Connectance Index	0.13	
System Omnivory Index	0.28	
Ecopath pedigree	0.47	
Shannon diversity index	0.92	

Ecological indicators of the Western Mediterranean Sea model

The biomass-based indicators showed a larger portion of fish in comparison with invertebrates in the ecosystem, and larger proportion of pelagic biomass in comparison with demersal biomass (Table 9) (Figure 47). In addition, a larger proportion of predatory biomass was observed when compared with the coastal sub-regional model. In accordance to trends in biomasses, a larger portion of catches came from the pelagic environment and from fish as in the case of the sub-regional model (Figure 48).

Overall, the trophic level of the community showed larger values than the sub-regional and local models, while the trophic level of the catch illustrated that the organisms targeted by the fishery were overall positioned in low and intermediate positions of the food web with low-medium levels of intrinsic vulnerabilities to fishing (Figure 49 and 50). These features were also highlighted by the size-based indicators of species in the catch, which respond to the dominance of the pelagic community in the ecosystem (Figure 51).

Table 9. Ecological indicators of the Western Mediterranean Sea model (1990s).

Indicator	Value	Units	Description
Biomass-based			
Total B	963.79	t/km2	Total biomass (B)
Commercial B	6.28	t/km2	Biomass (B) of commercial species
Fish B	4.28	t/km2	Biomass (B) of fish species
Invertebrates B	2.09	t/km2	Biomass (B) of invertebrate species
Invertebrates / Fish B	0.49		Biomass (B) of invertebrates over fish
Demersal B	0.91	t/km2	Biomass (B) of demersal species
Pelagic B	3.44	t/km2	Biomass (B) of pelagic species
Demersal / Pelagic B	0.27		Biomass (B) of demersal over pelagic species
Predatory B	0.39	t/km2	Biomass (B) of predatory organisms with trophic level ≥ 4
Kempton's Q	11.62		Kempton's diversity index (Q)
Shannon diversity	0.92		Shannon diversity index
Catch-based			
Total C	0.61	t/km2/year	Total catch (C)
Fish C	0.54	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of all fish species
Invertebrate C	0.06	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of all invertebrate species
Invertebrates / Fish C	0.11		Catch (C) of invertebrates over fish
Demersal C	0.14	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of demersal species
Pelagic C	0.44	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of pelagic species
Demersal / pelagic C	0.32		Catch (C) of demersal over pelagic species
Predatory C	0.090	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of predatory organisms with trophic level ≥ 4
Discards	0.07	t/km2/year	Total discarded catch
Trophic-based			
TL catch	3.31		Trophic level (TL) of the catch
MTI	3.83		Marine trophic index or trophic level (TL) of the catch including organisms with TL ≥ 3.25
TL community	1.21		Trophic level (TL) of the community
TL community 2	2.37		Trophic level (TL) of the community including organisms with TL ≥ 2
TL community 3.25	3.76		Trophic level (TL) of the community including organisms with TL ≥ 3.25
TL community 4	4.16		Trophic level (TL) of the community including organisms with TL ≥ 4
Species-based			
Intrinsic Vul. Index	41.63		Intrinsic Vulnerability Index of the catch
Endemics B	0.13	t/km2	Biomass (B) of endemic species in the community
Endemics C	0.029	t/km2/year	Endemic species in the catch (C)
IUCN species B	0.53	t/km2	Biomass (B) of IUCN-endangered species in the community
IUCN species C	0.07	t/km2/year	Proportion of IUCN-endangered species in the catch (C)
Mammals, birds & reptiles B	0.03	t/km2	Biomass (B) of marine mammals, seabirds and reptiles
Mammals, birds & reptiles C	0	t/km2/year	Catch (C) of marine mammals, seabirds and reptiles
Size-based			
ML of fish community	31.64	cm	Mean length (ML) of fish in the community
ML of fish C	44.19	cm	Mean length (ML) of fish in the catch (C)
MW of fish community	7.09	kg	Mean weight (MW) of the fish in the community
MW of fish C	14.60	kg	Mean weight (MW) of fish in the catch (C)
MLS of fish community	14.14	y	Mean life span (MLS) of fish in the community
MLS of fish C	12.85	y	Mean life span (MLS) of fish the catch (C)

Figure 47. Biomass-based indicators of the Western Mediterranean Sea food web model (histogram based on 100 Monte Carlo runs).

Figure 48. Catch-based indicators of the Western Mediterranean Sea food web model (histogram based on 100 Monte Carlo runs).

Keystone species of the Western Mediterranean Sea model

Of the three indicators used, Gulls and cormorans, Striped dolphins, Bottlenose dolphins, European lobster, Salema, Pelagic sharks, Other commercial shrimps, Common two-banded seabream, Swordfish, Other commercial decapods and Salps and other gelatinous zooplankton were identified as the groups with highest keystoneity (Figure 52).

When using the indicator by Libralato et al (2012), other groups with larger biomasses were identified (such as mesozooplankton and other macro-benthos and macrozooplankton), while when using Power et al. (2006) rare species were highlighted (such as Monk seals, Terns and Endangered and pelagic seabirds) (Table in Supplementary Material).

Mixed trophic impact analysis of the Western Mediterranean Sea model

The analysis (Figure 53) highlighted that each fleet had a negative impact on itself due to self-competition for resources. In addition, bottom trawl had a positive impact on purse seine and a negative impact on recreational and artisanal fisheries. Purse seine had a negative impact on recreational and longline fisheries and a positive impact on the trawl fisheries. Longline fisheries had positive impacts and trawl and purse seine fisheries, and a negative one on the recreational activity. Artisanal fisheries had a slight negative impact on the recreational fisheries, and a slight positive impact on trawlers. Recreational fisheries showed mainly a negative interaction with artisanal and longline fisheries. Therefore, we identified complex trade-offs between the main fleet sectors operating in the study area. In some cases those interactions were similar than the ones identified in the sub-regional model, and in other cases they were of different nature.

The MTI analyses highlighted larger impacts from trawling on several functional groups in the ecosystem, with negative impacts dominating (such as in demersal sharks and fishes, commercial crustaceans such as Norway lobster and bycatch such as Corals) (Figure 53). Due to depletion of competitors or predators, some groups were positively impacted by trawling, such as Bivalves and Gastropods, and the gelatinous groups (both jellyfishes and salps). Purse seiners mainly showed negative impacts on target species, and predators of those species such as dolphins and Bluefin tuna. The longline fishery showed largest impacts on bycatch species, such as Pelagic seabirds, Gulls and cormorants, and Marine turtles, aside from targeted species such as Swordfish. The artisanal fishery showed several large negative impacts on targeted species, predators of those species and bycatch (such as cetaceans groups) and positive impacts on invertebrate and fish competitors of target species or prey of affected predators, such as shrimps, cephalopods and less commercial fish species.

Recreational fisheries showed less widespread impacts, but larger negative impacts on their targeted species (such as pelagic fish and sharks and targeted demersal species).

Discussion and conclusions

In this deliverable we presented the result of all the static food-web models developed under Safenet WP4 representing marine ecosystems of the Mediterranean Sea, covering local, sub-regional and regional geographic scales. To our knowledge, this is the first time that food-web models in local areas of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea, such as in Cèrbere-Banyuls, Cap de Creus, Medes Islands, Gulf of Lions FRA and ZTB Argetario protected areas or management units are developed. This opens future opportunities to improve the models and develop temporal and spatial-temporal simulations (presented in *deliverables 4.3 and 4.4*). In addition, an important effort was employed to retrieve, integrate and evaluate available data to structure and parameterize all models according to a standardized meta-web (*deliverable 4.1*). This allowed us to assess the limitations and uncertainty of input data, and perform some uncertainty analyses on model output.

Local models: Mus, MPAs and FRAs

Results of the local MPAs, MUs and FRAs models were used to (1) characterize and compare the structure and functioning of each MPA management area; (2) assess differences/similarities between MPA management areas and among the three MPAs and two FRAs; and (3) assess if no-take management areas had noticeable traits impacts in the three areas and can be related to history, traits and compliance of protection. Overall, our comparative approach showed small differences between management areas in terms of ecosystem structure and functioning: FPA presented most positive effect of protection and were followed by PPAs. The effect of protection in neighbouring non-protected areas (UPA) was hardly noticeable in the three evaluated MPAs.

Our results showed that similarities were found between Cerbere-Banyuls and Medes Islands MPAs due to similarities in their configuration, enforcement and establishment. Cap de Creus Natural Park showed the least benefits from protection, likely due to the impact of recreational and artisanal fisheries. Our study illustrated that well-enforced Mediterranean MPAs can yield positive, but very local, impacts on the structure and functioning of marine ecosystems. To our knowledge, this work represents the first attempt to model management units within a protected area and provides the basis to assess the role of these areas within a network of MPAs using a food-web modelling approach. Our results suggested that enforcement can have an impact regarding potential benefits of MPAs at the local scale, and a lack of enforcement is noticeable in surrounding areas. These results highlighted the capability of the modelling approach to capture protection effects in such small areas despite limitations. This study also pointed out that protected areas can increase their maturity and resilience and show potential benefits for small-scale fisheries that act in their surroundings when these areas are well-enforced.

The food-web models developed to represent the Gulf of Lions FRA and the ZTB Argentario reflected the differences between the two ecosystems. While the Gulf of Lions is a continental-shelf and slope area, the ZTB Argentario represents a more coastal area. Therefore, ecological indicators yielded different results, and different keystone species were identified. The analyses of fishing fleet interactions within the local models helped us identified complex trade-offs between the main fleet sectors operating in the study areas, while they also revealed a high competition between them in terms of targeted commercial species. The analyses of model structure and functioning of both areas before and after the establishment of the regulations did not show noticeable effects of such measures to date.

Sub-regional and regional models

The sub-regional model of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea represents a coastal and continental shelf area of an exploited ecosystem of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea. Other studies already developed modelling initiatives in this area, such the one from Corrales and co-authors (Corrales et

al. 2015). However, this is the first time that the coastal area is explicitly included, and that MPAs are integrated into the context of a larger area. The development of such a sub-regional model allows the development of assessments of the potential benefits of the network of MPAs inside the modelled area and creates a great opportunity to develop analyses of the role of individual MUs and MPAs within a network and to assess their impacts at a sub-regional (e.g. Northwestern Mediterranean) and regional (e.g. Western Mediterranean) geographic scales.

Regarding the regional model covering the whole Western Mediterranean Sea, this is the first time that such a large food-web model with such detail has been created for the area. We developed a very comprehensive model of the Western Mediterranean basin with an acceptable quality that represents a baseline to pursue temporal and spatial-temporal simulations to test historical and future ecosystem and fisheries dynamics, allowing to include climate variability and change. The model adds to the capability of the scientific community of the Mediterranean Sea to further develop ecosystem analyses and forecasting scenarios under a global change context, and complements previous attempts (Piroddi et al. 2015, Piroddi et al. 2017).

Quality of the data to develop food-web models

Even though our work shows that quantitative food-web modelling techniques can be useful to assess MPAs effects on the structural and functional traits of marine ecosystems and their adjacent fisheries, some limitations were found during this study, mainly when dealing with the local scale modelling activities of the project.

One of the main hurdles was the lack of local data for some functional groups, as already identified in previous MPAs modelling studies (Prato et al., 2016; Valls et al., 2012). For example, literature including benthonic biomass estimations inside MPAs is mainly focused on sea urchin, gorgonian and Posidonia (e.g. Hereu et al., 2012; Schvartz and Labbe, 2012), but studies about other important benthic groups such as sponges or crustaceans are scarce.

Additionally, spatial-temporal series of catches and fleet distribution would improve the analysis how MPA effects potentially benefit recreational and artisanal fishery. We did not find studies of artisanal and recreations fishery, and could not find estimates of temporal catches in Cap de Creus and in Medes Islands MPAs. Collecting time series of fisheries activities surrounding MPAs is a monitoring priority, as previously highlighted (Prato et al., 2016; Valls et al., 2012).

Annexes – Supplementary material from the ecological models

All the supplementary material information can be downloaded from the following link:

<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/89jowmdizgk4dlq/AAAXJrG6-DEpLY98vGbEgvyta?dl=0>

Supplementary material – Cèrbere-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands MU models

Table 1. Input sources of information of the Management Units of Cèrbere-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands Ecopath models.

Table 2. Diet matrices of the Management Units of Cèrbere-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands Ecopath models.

Table 3. Functional groups of the Management Units of Cèrbere-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands Ecopath models and main inputs and outputs. TL: trophic level, OI: omnivory index, B: biomass, P: production, Q: consumption, EE: Ecotrophic efficiency, F: fishing mortality, Z: total mortality.

Table 4. Keystone indicators of the Management Units of Cèrbere-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands Ecopath models. KS1 (Libralato et al. 2006); KS2 (Power et al. 1996); KS3 (Valls et al. 2015).

Supplementary material – Cèrbere-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands MPA models

Table 5. Input sources of information of the MPAs of Cèrbere-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands Ecopath models.

Table 6. Diet matrices of the MPAs of Cèrbere-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands Ecopath models.

Table 7. Functional groups of the MPAs of Cèrbere-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands Ecopath models and main inputs and outputs. TL: trophic level, OI: omnivory index, B: biomass, P: production, Q: consumption, EE: Ecotrophic efficiency, F: fishing mortality, Z: total mortality.

Table 8. Keystone indicators of the MPAs of Cèrbere-Banyuls, Cap de Creus and Medes Islands Ecopath models. KS1 (Libralato et al. 2006); KS2 (Power et al. 1996); KS3 (Valls et al. 2015).

Supplementary material – FRAs Ecopath models

Table 9. Input sources of information of the FRA Gulf of Lions and ZTB Argentario Ecopath models.

Table 10. Diet matrices of the MPAs of the FRA Gulf of Lions and ZTB Argentario Ecopath models.

Table 11. Functional groups of the FRA Gulf of Lions and ZTB Argentario Ecopath models, main inputs and outputs. TL: trophic level, OI: omnivory index, B: biomass, P: production, Q: consumption, EE: Ecotrophic efficiency, F: fishing mortality, Z: total mortality.

Table 12. Keystone indicators of the FRA Gulf of Lions and ZTB Argentario Ecopath models. KS1 (Libralato et al. 2006); KS2 (Power et al. 1996); KS3 (Valls et al. 2015).

Supplementary material – Northwestern Mediterranean Sea Ecopath model

Table 13. Input sources of information of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea Ecopath models.

Table 14. Diet matrices of the MPAs of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea Ecopath models.

Table 15. Functional groups of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea Ecopath model, main inputs and outputs. TL: trophic level, OI: omnivory index, B: biomass, P: production, Q: consumption, EE: Ecotrophic efficiency, F: fishing mortality, Z: total mortality.

Table 16. Keystone indicators of the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea model. KS1 (Libralato et al. 2006); KS2 (Power et al. 1996); KS3 (Valls et al. 2015).

Supplementary material – Western Mediterranean Sea Ecopath model

Table 17. Input sources of information of the Western Mediterranean Sea Ecopath models.

Table 18. Diet matrices of the MPAs of the Western Mediterranean Sea Ecopath models.

Table 19. Functional groups of the Western Mediterranean Sea Ecopath model, main inputs and outputs. TL: trophic level, OI: omnivory index, B: biomass, P: production, Q: consumption, EE: Ecotrophic efficiency, F: fishing mortality, Z: total mortality.

Table 20. Keystone indicators of the Western Mediterranean Sea model. KS1 (Libralato et al. 2006); KS2 (Power et al. 1996); KS3 (Valls et al. 2015).

References

- Albouy C, Mouillot D, Rocklin D, Culioli JM, Le Loch F (2010) A trophic model to simulate the combined effect of artisanal and recreational fisheries on a Mediterranean ecosystem: the Bonifacio Straits Natural Reserve (Corsica, France). *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 412:207-221
- Christensen V (1995) Ecosystem maturity - towards quantification. *Ecological Modelling* 77:3-32
- Christensen V (1996) Managing fisheries involving predator and prey species. *Reviews in Fish Biology and Fisheries* 6:417-442
- Christensen V (2000) Indicators for marine ecosystems affected by fisheries. *Marine and Freshwater Research* 51:447-450
- Christensen V (2013) Ecological Networks in Fisheries: Predicting the Future? *Fisheries* 38:76-81
- Christensen V, Maclean J (2011) *Ecosystem Approaches to Fisheries: A Global Perspective*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge
- Christensen V, Pauly D (1992) ECOPATH II - A software for balancing steady-state ecosystem models and calculating network characteristics. *Ecological Modelling* 61:169-185
- Christensen V, Walters C (2004) Ecopath with Ecosim: methods, capabilities and limitations. *Ecological Modelling* 72:109-139
- Christensen V, Walters C, Pauly D, Forrest R (2008) Ecopath with Ecosim version 6. User Guide - November 2008. Lenfest Ocean Futures Project 2008:235 pp
- Cinuzzi F (2005) Caratterizzazione ambientale della Zona di Tutela Biologica (ZTB) "Argentario".
- Claudet J, Fraschetti S (2010) Human-driven impacts on marine habitats: A regional meta-analysis in the Mediterranean Sea. *Biological Conservation* 143:2195-2206
- Claudet J, Pelletier D, Jouvenel JY, Bachet F, Galzin R (2006) Assessing the effects of marine protected area (MPA) on a reef fish assemblage in a northwestern Mediterranean marine reserve: Identifying community-based indicators. *Biological Conservation* 130:349-369
- Coll M (2006) Trophic web modelling and ecological indicators for assessing ecosystem impacts of fishing in the Mediterranean Sea. PhD Thesis, Autonomous University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain
- Coll M, Akoglu E, Arreguín-Sánchez F, Fulton EA, Gascuel D, Heymans JJ, Libralato S, Mackinson S, Palomera I, Piroddi C, Shannon LJ, Steenbeek J, Villasante S, Christensen V (2015) Modelling dynamic ecosystems: venturing beyond boundaries with the Ecopath approach. *Reviews in Fish Biology and Fisheries* 25:413-424
- Coll M, Libralato S (2012) Contributions of food-web modelling for an Ecosystem Approach of Marine Resource Management in the Mediterranean Sea. *Fish and Fisheries* 13:60-88
- Coll M, Santojanni A, Palomera I, Tudela S, Arneri E (2007) An ecological model of the Northern and Central Adriatic Sea: Analysis of ecosystem structure and fishing impacts. *Journal of Marine Systems* 67:119-154
- Coll M, Steenbeek J (2017) Standardized ecological indicators to assess aquatic food webs: the ECOIND software plug-in for Ecopath with Ecosim models. *Environmental Modelling and Software* 89:120-130
- Colléter M, Valls A, Guitton J, Gascuel D, Pauly P, Christensen V (2015) Global overview of the applications of the Ecopath with Ecosim modelling approach using the EcoBase models repository. *Ecological Modelling* 302:42-53
- Corrales X, Coll M, Tecchio S, Bellido JM, Fernández AM, Palomera I (2015) Ecosystem structure and fishing impacts in the North-western Mediterranean Sea using a food-web model within a comparative approach. *Journal of Marine Systems* 148:183-199
- Corrales X, Ofir E, Coll M, Menachem G, Edelist D, Heymans JJ, Gal G (2017) Modeling the role and impact of alien species and fisheries on the Israeli marine continental shelf ecosystem. *Journal of Marine Systems* 170:88-102

- Di Franco A, Bodilis P, Piante C, Di Carlo G, Thiriet P, Francour P, Guidetti P (2014) L'engagement des pecheurs dans les aires marines protégées de Méditerranée, un élément clé du succes de la gestion de la peche artisanale. *Projet MedPAN Nord*. WWF-France.
- Finn JT (1976) Measures of ecosystem structure and function derived from analysis of flows. *Journal of Theroretical Biology* 56:363-380
- Font T, Lloret J (2011a) iological implications of recreational shore angling and harvest in a marine reserve: the case of Cape Creus. *Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 21:210-217
- Font T, Lloret J (2011b) Socioeconomic implications of recreational shore angling for the management of coastal resources in a Mediterranean marine protected area. *Fisheries Research* 108:214-217
- Fulton EA, Bax NJ, Bustamante RH, Dambacher JM, Dichmont C, Dunstan PK, Hayes KR, Hobday AJ, Pitcher R, Plagányi EE (2015a) Modelling marine protected areas: insights and hurdles. *Phil Trans R Soc B* 370:20140278
- Fulton EA, Boschetti F, Sporcic M, Jones T, Little LR, Dambacher JM, Gray R, Scott R, Gorton R (2015b) A multi-model approach to engaging stakeholder and modellers in complex environmental problems. *Environmental Science & Policy* 48:44-56
- Gell FR, Roberts CM (2003) Benefits beyond boundaries: the fishery effects of marine reserves. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 18:448–455
- Gómez S, Lloret J, Demestre M, Riera V (2006) The decline of the artisanal fisheries in Mediterranean coastal areas: the case of Cap de Creus (Cape Creus). *Coastal Management* 34:217-232
- Hereu B, Quintana X (2012) El fons marí de les illes Medes i el Montgrí: quatre dècades de recerca per a la conservació.
- Heymans JJ, Coll M, Libralato S, Morissette L, Christensen V (2014) Global Patterns in Ecological Indicators of Marine Food Webs: A Modelling Approach. *PLoS ONE* 9:e95845
- Heymans JJ, Coll M, Link JS, Mackinson S, Steenbeek J, Christensen V (2016) Best practice in Ecopath with Ecosim food-web models for ecosystem-based management. *Ecological Modelling* 331:173–184
- Iacono CL, Orejas C, Gori A, Gili JM, Requena S, Puig P, Ribó M (2012) Habitats of the Cap de Creus continental shelf and Cap de Creus canyon, northwestern Mediterranean. *En Seafloor geomorphology as benthic habitat* (pp. 457-469). Elsevier.
- Ivanoff P, Payrot J, Verdoit-Jarraya M (2010) A recreational fishery survey inside and outside a marine protected area (north-western mediterranean) over one year: typology, seasonal variability and reserve's influence. *Mémoire Master*. Univ. Montpellier.
- Libralato S, Christensen V, Pauly D (2006) A method for identifying keystone species in food web models. *Ecological Modelling* 195:153-171
- Libralato S, Coll M, Tempesta M, Santojanni A, Spoto M, Palomera I, Arneri E, Solidoro C (2010) Food-web traits of protected and exploited areas of the Adriatic Sea. *Biological Conservation* 143:2182–2194
- Ligas A, De Ranieri S, Micheli D, Reale B, Sartor P, Sbrana M, Belcari P (2010) Analysis of the landings and trawl survey time series from the Tyrrhenian Sea (NW Mediterranean). *Fisheries Research* 105:46-56
- Link J (2011) *Ecosystem-based fisheries Management: confronting tradeoffs*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge
- Link JS (2010) Adding rigor to ecological network models by evaluating a set of pre-balance diagnostics: a plea for PREBAL. *Ecological Modelling* 221:1580-1591
- Lloret J, Biton-Porsmoguer S, Carreño A, Di Franco A, Sahyoun R, Melià P, Claudet J, Ligas A, Belharet M, Calò A, Carbonara P, Coll M, Corrales X, Lembo G, Sartor P, Bitetto I, Vilas D, Piroddi C, Prato G, Charbonnel E, Bretto O, Hartmann V, Prats L, Font T (In press) Recreational and small-scale fisheries may pose a threat to vulnerable species in coastal and offshore waters of the western Mediterranean. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*

- Lloret J, Zaragoza N, Caballero D, Font T, Casadevall M, Riera V (2008a) Spearfishing pressure on fish communities in rocky coastal habitats in a Mediterranean marine protected area. *Fisheries Research* 94:84-91
- Lloret J, Zaragoza N, Caballero D, Riera V (2008b) Biological and socioeconomic implications of recreational boat fishing for the management of fishery resources in the marine reserve of Cap de Creus (NW Mediterranean). *Fisheries Research* 91:252-259
- Martín P, Maynou F, Stelzenmüller V, Sacanell M (2012) A small-scale fishery near a rocky littoral marine reserve in the northwestern Mediterranean (Medes Islands) after two decades of fishing prohibition. *Scientia Marina* 76:607-618
- Massutí E, Ordinas F, González N, Pérez A, Guijarro B, Fernández U (2008) INFORME DEL SEGUIMIENTO CIENTÍFICO DE LA ACCIÓN PILOTO RAI/AP-26/2007: PESCA EXPERIMENTAL CON ARTE DE ARRASTRE
- McClanahan TR, Mangi S (2000) Spillover of exploitable fishes from a marine park and its effect on the adjacent fishery. *Ecological Applications* 10:1792-1805
- Mellado López T (2006) Un Modelo trófico para la comunidad de algas fotófilas de las islas Medes. Universitat de Barcelona. MSc Thesis. 41 pp.,
- Micheli F (2004) Trajectories and correlated of community change in no-take Marine Reserves. *Ecological Applications* 14:1709-1723
- Pauly D (1980) On the interrelationships between natural mortality, growth parameters, and mean environmental temperature in 175 fish stocks. *Journal du Conseil International pour l'Exploration de la Mer* 39:175-192
- Pinnegar JK, Polunin NVC, Francour P, Badalamenti F, Chemello R, Harmelin-Vivien ML, Hereu B, Milazzo M, Zabala M, D'Anna G, Pipitone C (2000) Trophic cascades in benthic marine ecosystems: lessons for fisheries and protected-area management. *Environmental Conservation* 27:179-200
- Piroddi C, Coll M, Liqueste C, Macias Moy D, Greer K, Buszowski J, Steenbeek J, Danovaro R, Christensen V (2017) Historical changes of the Mediterranean Sea ecosystem: modelling the role and impact of primary productivity and fisheries changes over time. *Scientific Reports* 7:DOI: 10.1038/srep44491
- Piroddi C, Coll M, Steenbeek J, Moy DM, Christensen V (2015) Modelling the Mediterranean marine ecosystem as a whole: addressing the challenge of complexity. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 533:47-65
- Polovina JJ (1984) Model of a Coral-Reef Ecosystem .1. the Ecopath Model and Its Application to French Frigate Shoals. *Coral Reefs* 3:1-11
- Power ME, Tilman D, Estes JA, Menge BA, Bond WJ, Mills LS, Daily G, Castilla JC, Lubchenco J, Paine RT (1996) Challenges in the quest for keystones. *BioScience* 46:609-620
- Prato G (2016) Field monitoring and trophic modelling as management tools to assess ecosystem functioning and the status of high trophic level predators in Mediterranean MPAs. Université de Nice-Sophia Antipolis. PhD Thesis
- Prato G, Gascuel D, Valls A, Francour P (2014) Balancing complexity and feasibility in Mediterranean coastal food-web models: uncertainty and constraints. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 512:71-88
- Prats L (2016) Etude de la variabilité spatiale et temporelle dans la Réserve Naturelle Marine de Cerbère-Banyuls et à proximité : caractérisation de la pêche professionnelle, étude de l'effet réserve et des espèces à protéger (Msc thesis). Université de Pau et des Pays de L'Adour.
- Raimbault P, Durrieu de Madron X (2003) Research activities in the Gulf of Lion (NW Mediterranean) within the 1997–2001 PNEC project. *Oceanologica Acta* 26:291-298
- Ros J, Gili JM (2015) Four decades of research on the Medes Islands. . *Contributions to Science* 11:75-83
- Sacanell M (2012) Study on recreational fishing in the Medes Islands marine protected area. Tech Rep to Medes Islands Mar Reserv Manag Auth 52 pp

- Sala E, Aburto-Oropeza O, Paredes G, Parra I, Barrera JC, Dayton PK (2002) A general model for designing networks of marine reserves. *Science* 298:1991-1993
- Steenbeek J (2018a) Diet Calculator - Quick Reference Guide. Version 0.8.5, 11 June 2018. Safenet project - EU-DGMARE (MARE/2014/41), Barcelona
- Steenbeek J (2018b) MEDITS Data Explorer - Quick Reference Guide. Version 1.5.1, 26 June 2018. Safenet project - EU-DGMARE (MARE/2014/41), Barcelona
- Tudó P (2017) Unpubl. Data. Directorate of Fishing and Maritime Affairs, Government of Catalonia, Avinguda Diagonal 523-525, 08029 Barcelona, Spain.
- Ulanowicz RE, Puccia CJ (1990) Mixed trophic impacts in ecosystems. *Coenoses* 5:7-16
- UNEP-MAP-RAC/SPA (2013) Description of the ecology of the Gulf of Lions shelf and slope area and identification of the areas that may deserve to be protected. By Sardà, J.M.G. and Domínguez-Carrió, C. Ed. RAC/SPA, Tunis. 64pp.
- Valls A, Coll M, Christensen V (2015) Keystone species: towards an operational concept for marine biodiversity conservation. *Ecological Monographs* 85:29–47
- Valls A, Gascuel D, Guénette S, Francour P (2012) Modeling trophic interactions to assess the effects of a marine protected area: case study in the NW Mediterranean Sea. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 456:201-214
- Walters C (2000) Impacts of dispersal, ecological interactions, and fishing effort dynamics on efficacy of marine protected areas: how large should protected areas be? *Bulletin of Marine Science* 66:745-757